

GET International Research Journal Permission Page

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJORS IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT LAST MILE SCHOOLS

“I hereby grant the Guild of Educators in TESOL International Research Journal (GETIRJ) a nonexclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish, and publicly distribute copies of this thesis/dissertation in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the IPR policy, and any contractual obligations.”

“Specifically, I grant the following rights to GETIRJ:

1. To upload a copy of the work in the thesis database of the college/school/institute/department and any other database available on the internet.
2. To publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and
3. To give open access to the above-mentioned work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provisions of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293). Especially for teaching, scholarly, and research purposes”

MARIA HAYDE MARTINEZ
November 30, 2024

E- ISSN:2984-7184
P- ISSN: 2984-7176

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14496857
Volume 2 Issue 04

Recommended Citations: Martinez, M. H. (2024). LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJORS IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT LAST MILE SCHOOLS. In GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL (Vol. 2, Number 4, pp. 303–414). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14496857>

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION
MAJORS IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT
LAST MILE SCHOOLS**

A Dissertation
Presented to
The Faculty of the Graduate School
EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE
Manila, Philippines

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT
Major in Physical Education

MARIA HAYDE MARTINEZ

DECEMBER 2024

APPROVAL SHEET

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT** major in Physical Education, this dissertation entitled “**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJORS IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT LAST MILE SCHOOLS**” has been prepared and submitted by **MARIA HAYDE P. MARTINEZ.**

DR. LORNA A. ESPESO
Adviser

Approved by the Committee on Oral Examination with the grade of:
_____.

LINO C. REYNOSO, LPT, PhD.
Chair

ERNA A. LAHOZ, PhD.
Member

RODERICK C. TOBIAS, PhD.
Member

MARIA SHARON D. RICAMORA, PhD
Member

Comprehensive Examination Grade: _____
Date: _____

Accepted and approved in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, **DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT** Major in Physical Education.

Date: _____

LINO C. REYNOSO, LPT, PhD.
Dean Graduate School

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to our Almighty God, my savior, my strength and the source of all my knowledge and wisdom. My family for being my inspiration who are always there to support me in every step of the way.

I dedicate this achievement to my daughter Haiven Erich. She always reminds me of not giving up in every battle in life.

I consider myself very fortunate for having a family who always motivated me to keep on going whenever I feel like giving up.

Finally, to the non-P.E. major teaching physical education in last mile schools. Your dedication and commitment in teaching PE subject despite of the obstacles and challenges that you encounter in the last mile schools are genuinely motivating and incomparable. May you never stop giving your service to the young people and be part of achieving their dreams.

MARIA HAYDE P. MARTINEZ

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, giving the highest praise and love to God Almighty, who has granted countless blessing, knowledge, and opportunity in completing this important undertaking during the course of this research.

To DepEd Division of Rizal for granting permission to conduct the research.

To Dr. Lorna A. Espeso, for her unwavering support and motivation to pursue and finish this dissertation.

To Dr. Lino C Reynoso, Dean of the Graduate School, for his outstanding supervision and concern to the researcher.

To Dr. Maria Sharon D. Ricamora for her generosity in sharing her expertise.

To the panelist, thank you for your ideas and suggestions that made this paper publishable.

To the researcher's family and friends, who provided moral support and encouragement to make this research possible.

MARIA HAYDE P. MARTINEZ

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the significant experiences and the challenges that the non-PE major teachers faced in teaching Physical Education in the last-mile schools. With the limited number of teachers handling learners in last-mile schools, it is unavoidable to assign subjects that are not the expertise of the teacher which may possibly affect the teaching and learning process.

The participants of the study came from the 4 junior high schools only. The available number of non- PE majors teaching physical education in the last mile school in the Province of Rodriguez were 10 teachers from National High School. This study utilized Phenomenological Research Design. The Purposive Sampling was used to recruit the participants. The study uses semi-structured, open-ended questions for the data collection phase of the study. Using the Thematic Analysis of Data.

The strategies employed by non-physical education teachers to address challenges in teaching Physical Education showcases the power of creativity, detailed planning, and interdisciplinary approaches. The fact that some of the resources are not available or limited in the last mile school, teachers try to innovate and become resilient. The study reveals that learners enjoy PE subject and because of that the teacher responds to students' energy level, outdoor enthusiasm, and hands-on learning preferences with high spirit. These insights provide valuable considerations for educators seeking to enhance the overall learning experience, fostering enthusiasm and engagement among students in last-mile schools.

Keywords:

Last mile Schools, Phenomenological, Thematic Analysis, Interdisciplinary approach, hands-on learning preferences.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
<i>Title Page</i>	304
<i>Approval Sheet</i>	305
<i>Dedication</i>	306
<i>Acknowledgement</i>	307
<i>Abstract</i>	308
<i>Table of Contents</i>	309
<i>List of Appendices</i>	310
INTRODUCTION	
Introduction	311
Guiding Framework	316
Statement of Purpose	316
Significance of the Study	316
Scope and Delimitation	318
Definition of Terms	319
METHODOLOGY	
Research Design	320
Research Locale	321
Participants of the Study	321
Population Sample and Sampling Technique	324
Research Instrument	326
Data Gathering Procedure	327
Thematic Analysis of Data	328
Stages of Data Analysis	330
Trustworthiness of Data	331
Ethical Consideration	332
RESULTS AND ANALYSIS	
Theme One: Dive into Enthusiasm and a Home Run in Physical Education (PE) Activities	337
Theme Two: Explosive Punch in Teaching Fusion	342
Theme Three: Knock-out in Space for Physical Education Class	348
Theme Four: Game over in the Resources	352
Theme Five: Dive into Challenges of Integrating Technology	357
Theme Six: Grand Slam to Resilience and Passion In Teaching Physical Education	363

Theme Seven: Unleashing Potential through Adaptive Physical Education Teaching	370
Theme Eight: Teamwork between School and Community	375
Theme Nine: Game Plan in Addressing the Challenges	382
Summary of Findings	393
REFERENCES	402

LIST OF APPENDICES

	Page
Appendix A. Letters	406
Appendix B. Participants Profile	407
Appendix C. Ethical Review Certificate	408
Appendix D. Pictures	109
Appendix E. Certificate of Language Editing	
Appendix F. Proof of Consultation	
Appendix G. Curriculum Vitae	411

INTRODUCTION

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and in the future. They recognize that ending poverty and other deprivations must go together with strategies that improve health and education, reduce inequality, and spur economic growth.

Goal 4 – Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education ensures inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all. “The World is Falling Far Behind in Achieving Quality Education”, without additional measures, by 2030: 84 million children and youth will be out of school, 300 million students will lack basic numeracy/literacy skills, and only 1 in 6 countries will achieve the universal secondary school completion target.

The quality of education is racing behind due to low and lower-middle-income countries facing a nearly \$100 Billion Annual Financing Gap to reach their education targets.

The challenge in the quality of education across the world is still rising due to interrelated factors which if not mended immediately may provide unfavorable results.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

As of August 24, 2023, DepEd said the total number of enrolled students for the School Year (SY) 2023-2024 has reached 20,093,611. The highest number of enrollees is from Region IV-A with 3,265,523 followed by the National Capital Region with 2,402,858 and Region III with 2,177,726.

With these numbers of enrollment, several issues in the educational status of the country need to be addressed. According to Magsambol (2022) to head the agency (DepEd) is not an easy job. Experts have said that the country's poor education quality was a result of decades of neglect and underinvestment.

Rappler listed the issues to be addressed as the country recovers from the disruption in education brought on by the pandemic. It mentioned "Hire more teachers, aides" The Philippine Business for Education Executive Director Love Basillote, hire more teachers and teaching aides for students to "recover from learning losses." Lawmakers and senators said that administrative work should be off-loaded from them so they could focus on teaching.

In addition, ACT Teachers Party-list mentioned "the lack of teachers and education support personnel is a critical issue that needs to be addressed immediately. It directly affects the quality of education and support services that students receive.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Amidst all the challenges the education sector of the country is facing, a positive outlook is still on the rise for our learners of the future.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) developed the Last Mile Schools Program which aims to address the gaps in resources and facilities of schools that are in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas.

In addition to this, DepEd Memorandum No. 059, s. 2019 entitled “Prioritizing the Development of the Last Mile Schools in 2020-2021: Reaching Out and Closing the Gap” was released in May 2019 to formalize the efforts and make official the actions taken in line with the Last Mile Schools Program. The Last Mile School Program from the previous DepEd Secretary Leonor Briones, is part of the Future framework in line with the Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022 under the Duterte Administration.

It itemizes the indicators to be used in identifying a school as among the Last Mile Schools as well as the specific programs, projects, and activities that address the needs of the Last Mile Schools.

Last mile schools are identified as *1. Having less than four classrooms, 2. With makeshift or nonstandard rooms, 3. Absence of electricity, 4. Have not been allocated funds for repairs or new construction projects in the last four years, 5. With a travel distance*

of more than one hour from the town center, or with the difficulty of terrain, 6. Having multigrade classes/rooms, 7. With less than five teachers, 8. Having a population of fewer than 100 learners, and, 9. With more than 75% Indigenous People (IP) learners.)

With the limited number of teachers handling learners in last-mile schools, it is unavoidable to assign subjects that are not the expertise of the teacher which may possibly affect the teaching and learning process.

Based on the study of Macasias (2022) the level of knowledge and skills of non-MAPEH major teachers teaching Physical Education along Social and Ballroom Dances as perceived by the teachers and department heads rated “fair” which can be interpreted as not very knowledgeable and skilled in teaching the different competencies in social and ballroom dances.

According to Hobbs and Porsche (2021) teaching out-of-field is a phenomenon where teachers and qualifications (Ingersoll 1999; Hobbs 2013). This may refer to teaching subjects, year levels, or school types without necessary qualifications, certification, or specialization.

Physical Education is part of the spiral curriculum of the K-12 program (junior and senior high school) which seeks to develop students’ skills in accessing, synthesizing, and evaluating informed

decisions, enhancing, and advocating their own and others' fitness and health.

According to the National Board for Professional Standards, teachers must be skilled in their subject areas, as such, the physical education teacher must be a good athlete and an excellent role model for the students. S/he must reflect good health, physical coordination, and vitality. S/he will be confident and strong, physically fit, and be able to demonstrate techniques needed for a competitive and exercise routine.

Due to this educational situation, teachers handling subjects that are not majors in their own specializations are experiencing different challenging encounters which makes teaching performance more unpredictable in terms of efficiency and effectiveness.

Another issue for teachers assigned in last-mile schools is the utilization of Educational Technology for which access is also a challenge. The promotion of education for all is not possible without the intervention of technology which makes learning more interactive and engaging, without the internet, communication, and access to resources holistic learning is impossible.

Guiding Framework

This research discovered the unique experiences of non-major teachers in teaching Physical Education teachers assigned in last-mile schools, and the utilization of educational technology in teaching Physical Education among junior high school learners.

Using Phenomenological Research Design, this study explored the lived experiences of non-PE Majors Teachers assigned at last mile schools and teaching Physical Education.

Statement of Purpose

The main purpose of this research is to explore the significant experiences and the challenges that the Non-PE major teachers faced in teaching Physical Education in the last-mile schools.

Significance of the Study

In the completion of this research study, the community at large will benefit from this kind of academic endeavor. This will

serve as a guiding model for promoting quality education among non-major teachers assigned at last-mile schools.

This research can also benefit individuals and groups:

Non-Physical Education Teachers teaching in last-mile schools, this research can serve as instructional support in crafting instructional materials, lesson planning, remediation, and intervention, patterned on the culture of the IP learners.

TIC/Principal/PSDS of last-mile schools, to provide necessary and suitable technical assistance to fully equip teachers on teaching strategies, coping mechanisms, necessary preparations, mental state, etc. to deliver quality education for them.

LGU/Municipal Government Officials to extend government programs and projects to last-mile schools, and teachers for academic benefits and support educational technology as part of the innovation in instruction and curriculum.

Researcher, this research can widen the researcher's perspective on teaching Physical Education as the researcher is exposed on teachers with different specialization and applies their own teaching philosophies which can create new teaching strategies and methodologies in teaching the subject.

Future researcher, the outcome of this study can be used for future research studies to assess the implementation of the instructional plan proposed in this research. This can also serve as

a basis for evaluation of curricular offerings, most especially for learners and schools located in last-mile.

Scope and Delimitation

This research is only limited to the lived experiences of the participants of non-physical Education teachers located at last-mile schools in Montalban, Rizal.

There are 4 national high schools in the vicinity of Rodriguez, Rizal which are categorized as last-mile schools:

SCHOOLS	PARTICIPANTS
National High School -A	3
. National High School -B	2
. National High School -C	3
. National High School -D	2
Total	10

The target participants for this research study are 10 Non-Physical Education major teachers among the 4 last-mile schools presented above. Purposive sampling is used with Phenomenology as the research design. Creswell (1998) recommends 5-20 and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6 or when the saturation of data is reached.

The locale of the study is the participant's respective school, home, or any comfortable place or modality (face-to-face or online) the participant' is comfortable. The study mainly relies on the

participants' narrations of experiences. The view and analysis of the researcher is based only on the responses of the participants during the conduct of the study.

An interview guide is to be used as the main data-gathering tool and Unstructured Interview will be employed as the method of data collection.

Definition of Terms

The important words in this study are defined operationally.

Educational Technology – refers to the technology utilized by the participants in teaching Physical Education subjects.

Instructional Plan – refers to an action plan to be proposed by the researcher on how teaching non-specialized area of expertise to be delivered in classroom.

Last-mile Schools – refers to schools located in far-flung areas and one of the chosen characteristics of participants in this study.

Lived Experiences – refers to the actual phenomenon that exists among the chosen participants in this research.

Non-physical education major - one who is not taking a particular subject or course as their main subject of study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a Phenomenological Research Design to describe the lived experiences of the participants and uncover certain phenomena that may reveal truths about situations and real life. It aids in eliciting, describing, exploring, and analyzing their experiences as non-physical Education teachers.

Phenomenology, as a research methodology, is uniquely positioned to learn from the experiences of others. A type of qualitative research that focuses on the investigation of a person's lived experiences in the world. According to Neubauer, Witkop, and Varpio (2019), it is commonly described as the study of phenomena as they manifest in our experience, the way we perceive and understand phenomena, and the meaning phenomena have in our experience.

The goal of this method is to collect the participants' lived experiences to explain them from the participants' perspective and to help in making conclusions based on the observed phenomenon.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the vicinity of the province of Rodriguez, Rizal. A first-class, urban municipality in the province of Rizal. Located on the slopes of the Sierra Madre Mountain range. It is composed of 11 barangays which are in the lower and upper portions of the province.

Barangay San Jose, Burgos, Geronimo, Manggahan, San Rafael, Rosario, and Barangay San Isidro is in the lower portions while Barangay Macabud, Puray, Macabud, and Mascap are in the mountains, and the schools included in this study is in these barangays.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were non-physical education majors teaching Physical Education in Junior high schools located at last-mile schools in the province of Montalban, Rizal.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

According to the records of the DepEd Montalban District Office, there were 18 Non-Physical Education teachers assigned among the 9 elementary and junior last-mile schools.

The participants of the study came from the 4 junior high schools only. The available number of non- PE major teaching physical education in the last mile school in the Province of Rodriguez were 3 teachers from National High School A, 2 teachers from National High School B, 3 teachers from National High School C and 2 teachers from National High School D. The approximate number of participants are 10 non-Physical education teachers teaching Physical Education at last mile schools. They were contacted using social media and referrals from other teachers familiar to the researcher.

During the recruitment of the participants the researcher made sure that there are no vulnerable participants involved in the study. Individual who has illness, disability and pregnant woman are excluded from participating in the study.

To get acquainted with the participants here are some of the information that they have. Teacher A is a female teacher, 40 years of age and handling grade 7,8 and 9 she was once a science teacher for 2 years. She is a biology major and for almost 8 years she was assigned to teach Physical Education at Last Mile School.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Next is Teacher B a female teacher and at a very young age of 29 she was deployed as a PE teacher in one of the last mile schools in Montalban and its her 2nd year in teaching. She is a TLE major. But she never experienced to teach TLE. Teacher C is the next participant. She is a 35-year-old male teacher handling PE subject in grade 7,8,9, and 10. He is a TLE major and has been in the field of teaching in Last Mile School for 4 years. His first year of teaching he handles TLE subjects. Next in line is Teacher D, a male teacher with a degree of Bachelor of Education major in Social Studies. 28 years of age and have a 1-year experience in teaching at the last mile school. He handles grade 7 and 8. Teacher E is a female teacher, 45 years of age. She is a Filipino major and for almost 8 years she manages to teach Physical Education at the last mile school and only have 2 years' experience in teaching Filipino. Another participant is Teacher F, a female teacher who is 38 years of age. She is now in her 5th year of teaching Physical Education in Last Mile School even though she is a science major. She never have a chance to teach her major subject. Teacher G is a female teacher with a degree of Bachelor of Science in Education major in Mathematics. She is 42-year-old and handling PE subject in grade 8 and 9. She is now on her 5th year of teaching in Last Mile school. She was once a Mathematics teacher for 1 year. Teacher H is a

female teacher handling PE subject in grade 7,8,9, and 10. At the age of 36, she is now in her 3rd year of teaching in Last Mile School and at the start of her teaching career she never experience teaching Science as her major. Next is Teacher I, a 37-year-old female teacher who are now in her 4th year of teaching PE in last mile school. She is handling grade 7,8 and 9 and her major is TLE. The last participants is Teacher J who is currently handling PE subjects from grade 8,9 and 10. She is 39 year old and have a 6 years teaching experience in last mile school. She is a Social Studies major, and she experienced teaching Social Studies for 2 years and for almost 4 years she always teach PE subject since she is incline into sports.

Population Sample and Sampling Technique

Purposive Sampling was used in this study, it was used by qualitative researchers to recruit participants who can fully provide in-depth and detailed information about a certain phenomenon under investigation.

The researcher made a preliminary listing of Junior High Schools that were classified as last-mile schools and coordination between the school representative and the researcher is arranged.

The targeted participants of this research were the 10 teachers from last-mile schools who are non-PE majors teaching PE subjects.

Eligibility Criteria

The participants were chosen based on set exclusion and inclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria along with exclusion criteria, make up the selection or eligibility criteria used to rule in or out the target population for a research study. The eligibility criteria for the participants of the study are as follows:

- Graduate of bachelor's in education
- Non-Physical Education major
- Presently teaching Physical Education subject in High School Level
- Bonafide teacher in a Last mile public school

Vulnerable groups like pregnant woman, senior citizen and impaired physical functioning are excluded in the study.

Withdrawal Criteria

During the recruitment process, the researcher informed the participants that they may discontinue their participation in the research study anytime they want without any sanction. If the participants withdraw after the interview, the researcher will seek permission from the participant if they allow the continued use of their data. If the participant does not agree, the researcher will remove the data and exclude it from the study.

During the interview, the participants have the freewill not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress because of the sensitive nature of the topic. The researcher made sure that the priority during the study is the welfare of the participants.

Research Instrument

The study used semi-structured, open-ended questions for the data collection phase of the study. Each participant was asked 9 questions in relation to the problem statement of the study and follow-up questions are also considered for clarification of answers.

When the participant cannot answer the questions, the researcher rephrases the question for clarity and easy comprehension.

The duration of the interview was not limited to a certain time. The reason for this is that the researcher aimed to conduct the interviews in a manner that they would occur like a casual conversation between the participants, so that the interviewee is not limited in expressing their thoughts and sharing their experiences regarding the research topic. Consequently, the researcher was able to extract natural raw data as much as possible.

Data Gathering Procedure

1. A permit to conduct a study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Rizal as a protocol for data gathering among DepEd schools in Rizal.
2. The consent of the participants in the study was considered before the start of the procedure. A consent form is signed by them to signify their willingness to be part of the interview process.
3. During the recruitment process the researcher made sure that there are no vulnerable groups involved in the study.
4. Upon approval, the scheduling of interviews was done for a systematic flow of procedure and instruction. The researcher asked for the list of last-mile schools in the Sub-office of Montalban in Rodriguez, Rizal.
5. The conduct of interviews was done online and face-to-face depending on the comfort of the chosen participants of the study.
6. After all target participants was interviewed the researcher transcribed the interview in preparation for coding and data analysis.

7. A simple token of appreciation was given by the researcher to the participants.

Verification

In this step, the researcher met again with the participants to double check the accuracy of their transcriptions and to present the essence of their lived experience if it truthfully and honestly express their shared reality so as reliability and credibility of the essence of the studied phenomenon was confirmed by the participants themselves

Thematic Analysis of Data

This research followed the data analysis and coding procedures suggested by Creswell (2009) and Esterberg (2002). Specifically, Esterberg (2002) suggested that open coding is a process where “you work intensively with your data, line by line, identifying themes and categories that seem of interest.”

Creswell (2009) mandated the traditional approach in the social sciences that allows the codes to emerge during the data analysis. Once the data from this research were examined through an open coding process, the researcher reviewed the codes for emerging themes in the data.

This study followed Creswell's (2009) six steps during the data analysis process and, although these steps are described in linear order, Creswell described "an interactive practice" to analysis.

Thematic Analysis was used to examine any piece of writing or occurrence of recorded communication from the participants' experiences, equipped with a summative approach used to interpret meaning from the content of text data and, thus, adhere to the naturalistic paradigm. Summative content analysis entails counting and comparing items, usually keywords or content, and then interpreting the underlying context.

Data gathered through interviews was recorded and analyzed to identify patterns that emerged from the experiences and interpreted to locate patterns that will serve as the foundation for new discoveries.

The data from the selected participants are analyzed and undergo the coding process. The researcher searched through each participant's statements that are relevant and meaningful. The units of meaning are formed into themes and summarized.

From the thematic analysis, a large set of themes emerged, and these will be reduced by conducting an in-depth interpretative analysis with an aim to discover the lived experiences of non-Physical Education major teaching in last-mile schools.

Stages of Data Analysis

1. Read through the data. This is the “get to know your data” stage reflected on the overall meaning to gain a general sense of the information and ideas that the participants conveyed.
2. Organizing the raw data was broken down into groups of words and phrases by highlighting and labeling them using a coding process.
3. Organizing the materials into segments by taking the text data and segmenting sentences into categories. I labeled those categories with terms based on the actual language of the participants.
4. Generate codes for the descriptions, which then lead to generalizing a small number of categories or themes. Then I analyzed the themes that emerged and gathered the various cases into a general description for this case.
5. Advance how the description of the themes was represented in the qualitative narrative. I merged the emergent themes into narrative passages so that the findings emerged logically from the participants’ responses.
6. Interpret the meaning of the data from the raw data up to the secondary and primary themes. During my own interpretation process, my experience as a PE teacher helped me in understanding the concept of teaching as well as sharing almost the same experiences with the participants.

Trustworthiness of Data

In establishing trustworthiness (Erlandson, Harris, Skipper, & Allen, 1993), several methods were used in this study. To ascertain credibility, the researcher used prolonged engagement and consistent observation while doing the interview to produce findings that are unbiased, and representative of the information provided by the participants. The audio taped interviews and observation were used to increase credibility.

Follow-up questions were asked to identify additional aspects that can make a difference to the provided information and to confirm that both of us understand each other.

Confirmability is the neutrality or the degree of findings that are consistent and could be repeated (Polit & Beck, 2014). It is critical for other researchers to be able to duplicate the results in order to demonstrate that the results are the result of independent research methodologies rather than intentional or unconscious bias (Devault, 2019).

In the context of this study the researcher guarantees an audit trail to ensure the confirmability of this research. The researcher provides a detailed and comprehensive list of procedures to ensure the list track of records throughout the conduct of this study were reserved as for the evidence in to elude from biases and ensure that this study is not from the researcher own perspective and interest.

Further, the researcher asked assistance from her research adviser to review her work.

Transferability concerns the aspect of applicability. As a researcher, it is the duty of the researcher to give a "thick description" of the participants and the study procedure so that the reader can decide whether the findings are applicable to the context (Korstjens & Albine Moser 2018). In the context of this study, the researcher provides a "thick description" of the participants and the procedure of this study so that the other researchers can determine whether the results of this study applicable to transfer to other context or setting

Ethical Consideration

This research is done with a strict commitment to the ethical protocols and guidelines. The researcher religiously seeks the corresponding approval required to complete this study from key school officials. Since qualitative research flows from the opportunity to engage with the participants, the researcher made sure that there is no physical contact, harm or discomfort on the part of the participants. The researcher ensures that there is no psychological, social or economic risks that the participants might experience during the interview and until the end of the study. The confidentiality of the participants is protected to respect the participants privacy.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

The participants are all voluntary and there is no compensation, gift or any incentives that will significantly impact their physical, psychological or economic well-being that might also change their perception about the study. The benefit that they will gain in this research is that it can serve as their instructional support in crafting instructional materials, lesson planning, remediation, and intervention patterned on the culture of the students in the last mile schools.

The community at large will benefit from this kind of academic endeavor. This will encourage community participation in shaping PE programs that resonate with cultural values. strive to heighten awareness and appreciation for the pivotal role of physical education in building resilient, passionate, and healthy communities.

This study was approved by the DDOSC-REC. They may be reached via email rec@ddosc.edu.ph or through mobile number at 0998-571-7507.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this chapter, the researcher purposely utilized the principle of bracketing and horizontalization. The analysis of data presented in this chapter was supported by the researcher's field notes and the participants' transcription of interview.

The researcher is accustomed to the lived experiences of non-physical education majors in teaching students from last mile schools. As a researcher delving into the realm of non-physical education majors teaching in last mile schools, her journey began with a genuine curiosity to understand the unique challenges and experiences faced by educators in these settings. Her own academic background lies outside the realm of physical education, which added a personal touch to her exploration. Prior to embarking on this research, she found herself questioning the disparities in educational opportunities and outcomes among students, especially those in last mile schools. She sought to unravel the lived experiences of non-physical education majors who found themselves teaching in these contexts, where the landscape is often marked by resource limitations, diverse student needs, and a myriad of socio-economic challenges. The researcher's initial interactions with

teachers who did not have a specialized background in physical education revealed a spectrum of emotions – from initial apprehension to eventual adaptation and growth. One common thread was the genuine desire to make a positive impact on the lives of their students, despite not being experts in the field of physical education. Living through the narratives of these educators, The researcher witnessed their commitment to fostering holistic development, even in the absence of traditional resources. Many shared instances of innovative teaching methods, such as incorporating basic exercises into regular class routines or utilizing outdoor spaces creatively to facilitate physical activities. The challenges they faced were palpable. These teachers grappled with limited access to sports equipment, inadequate infrastructure, and the need for continuous professional development in the field of physical education. Despite these hurdles, their stories reflected resilience and a determination to provide students with opportunities for physical well-being and growth. One key aspect that emerged from my interviews and observations was the adaptability of non-physical education majors. Many recounted how they learned on the job, seeking guidance from colleagues, attending workshops, and leveraging online resources to enhance their understanding of physical education principles. Through this research, the researcher discovered the transformative power of educators who, driven by a

passion for teaching, transcended their academic backgrounds to create impactful learning environments. The narratives of these non-specialized physical education teachers shed light on the importance of holistic education and the role of adaptability in bridging gaps in educational disparities. In conclusion, the researcher personal journey into exploring the experiences of non-physical education majors teaching in last mile schools has been enlightening. It reinforced the notion that dedication and adaptability can indeed pave the way for positive change, even in challenging educational contexts. As educators continue to navigate the complexities of teaching in last mile schools, their stories serve as a testament to the transformative potential of education, irrespective of one's academic specialization.

The data produced by the study are presented in this arrangement: Theme, Sample Responses, and the Participants. Such arrangement of data is structured from research problems. The researcher made sense of the responses of the participants in order to address the central questions of the study.

1. How does the non-PE major describe their experiences in teaching Physical Education in last mile school?

Two themes were described namely: (1) **Dive into Enthusiasm and a Home Run win in Physical Education (PE) Activities:** (2) **Explosive Punch in Teaching Fusion**

Theme 1: Dive into Enthusiasm and a Home Run win in Physical Education (PE) Activities

This theme called our attention to the students’ enthusiasm and engagement in Physical Education Activities and their preference for hands-on, active learning in the last mile schools.

1. Experiences of non-PE major in teaching Physical Education in last mile schools		
Themes	Sample Responses	Participants
1. Dive into Enthusiasm and a Home Run win in Physical Education (PE) Activities	<i>“They are very active. Gustong gusto nila yung subject na PE. Gusto nila yung lumalabas naglalaro nag PE basta yung lumalabas ng room tapos kapag PE excited talaga sila kasi alam nilang lalabas sila.</i>	Teacher A handling Grade7,8, and 9.
	<i>“They are highly energetic and truly enjoy the Physical Education subject. They particularly like going outdoors and playing during PE. Whenever they leave the classroom for PE, they are genuinely excited because they know they will be going outside. I really make an effort to engage them in PE activities.</i>	
	<i>“Masaya sila at excited sila kasi lalabas sila. Pero kapag discussion sa classroom hindi lumalabas sa isipan nila yung mga terms na ginagamit pero kapag lumabas na sila may mga sarili silang terms kapag naglalaro na sila duon nalalaman na nila sa application”.</i>	Teacher B handling Grade 9 and 10

	<p><i>“Magaling sila sa physical activity kaysa sa mental activity. Kapag PE class nakikita mo yung excitement sa mata nila na magengage sa physical activity na ibibigay mo sa kanila. Almost 100 % ng mga bata sa Grade 10 nagparticipate sa mga physical activity. Motivated sila”.</i></p> <p><i>“They excel in physical activities compared to mental activities. In PE class, you can see the excitement in their eyes as they engage in the physical activities you provide. Almost 100% of the Grade 10 students participate in these physical activities. They are highly motivated”.</i></p> <p><i>“Ang mga bata po ay excited sila lalo na kpag sports especially kapag actual na naexperience nila yng sports. Inaantok kasi sila kapag theoretical mas motivated sila kapag actual. Mahirap din dahil wala kaming mga gamit kaya naiaaply nalang nila tuwing intramurals nmin dun ko sya naipapasok”.</i></p> <p><i>“ They are excited about sports especially if they experience it. They feel sleepy if I only teach theories they are more motivated if there is an actual game. It is very difficult to us because we lack of equipment they just apply their learning in sports during intramurals.</i></p> <p><i>“Actually mas active sila kpag PE time na mas gusto nila ang PE kaysa sa ibang component like music art and health. Kasi mas enjoy sila lalo na kapag sinabi mo na maglalaro ng Volleyball. Gusto</i></p>	<p>Teacher G handling Grade 8 and 9.</p> <p>Teacher F handling Grade 7 and 8.</p>
--	---	---

	<p><i>nila yung kumikilos gumagalaw ayaw nila ng nakaupo lng".</i></p> <p><i>"In fact, they are more active during PE time, and they prefer PE over other components like music, art, and health. They enjoy it more, especially when you mention playing volleyball. They appreciate activities that involve movement and dislike just sitting down".</i></p> <p><i>"Tuwing PE sobrang sigla nila. Parang gusto nilang ilabas lahat ng energy nila sa oras nayun. Para silang mga bata na nakalabas sa playground. Sa panahaon ngyn ang mga bata mas gusto nil ana sila ang kumikilos at gumagawa. Kaya kapag PE na nagmamadali na silang lumabas ng classroom. Gusto din nila na pinapanood sila ng mga tao habang nagpeperform. Ang mahalaga lahat sila ay active at walang inaantok sa PE.</i></p> <p><i>"During PE, they are extremely energetic. It's as if they want to release all their energy during that time. They act like children set free in a playground. Nowadays, kids want to be the ones moving and doing things, so when PE comes around, they are genuinely excited and eager to go outside immediately. They also enjoy being seen by many people while performing. Most importantly, none of the kids fall asleep because it's all about being active".</i></p> <p><i>"Masaya sila sa PE lively very attentive sympre may mga bata din nman na ayaw kumilos pro most of them well motivated sila. Yan ang</i></p>	<p>Teacher C handling Grade 7,8,9,10.</p> <p>Teacher D handling Grade 7 and 8</p>
--	--	---

	<p><i>inaabangan nila arts and Pe pro Music at health hindi masyado".</i> <i>"They are happy during PE, lively, and very attentive. Of course, there are some children who are not inclined to move much, but most of them are well-motivated. That's what they look forward to—arts and PE. However, they are not as enthusiastic about music and health".</i></p> <p><i>"Interested po sila mam. Feeling ko mas enjoy nila ang PE kysa sa Music and Arts. Nakikipag participate po sila lahat. Lahat naman sila ay participative pagdating sa PE class".</i> <i>"They are interested, ma'am. I feel that they enjoy PE more than Music and Arts. They actively participate in everything. All of them are participative when it comes to PE class".</i></p> <p><i>"Ang tumatak sa kanila kapag PE class na may pagka terror yung teacher nila. Kaya behave sila. Marunong po sila sumunod sa instructions. No choice po sila kundi sumunod".</i></p>	<p>Teacher handling Grade 8,9, and 10</p> <p>E</p>
--	--	--

In this theme, the participants highlights the students high energy levels, genuine excitement for outdoor activities during PE, and their preference for hands-on, active learning. The results also touch upon the contrast between their responsiveness in PE class compared to other subjects like music and art, emphasizing their preference for movement-based activities. The role of the teacher's approach, particularly in PE, is also mentioned as a contributing

factor to the students' behavior and participation. Overall, the theme revolves around the positive and energetic atmosphere created by PE activities in contrast to other classroom settings.

It is fascinating to note that students from last mile schools prefer PE subject because they love to move, which is the main objective of physical education. This highlights the dynamic nature of learning and the necessity of adjusting teaching methods to align with individual student preferences and strengths. Despite potential difficulties in comprehending theoretical concepts in a traditional classroom setting, these students demonstrate notable enthusiasm and engagement during PE activities. The joy, motivation, and energy exhibited in physical activities underscore the importance of integrating such sessions into their curriculum.

In this theme, the mention of students' excitement about being active during PE and their responsiveness to a somewhat strict teaching approach implies that a structured and disciplined environment contributes to their learning experience. This reinforces the idea that a balance between enthusiasm, enjoyment and discipline contributes to a positive and effective educational atmosphere.

Students' Enthusiasm and Engagement in Physical Education (PE) Activities are more directed to a sense of more and an attachment to the form of activity even though no one instructs it

(Pratiwi, 2019). If it is applied to the physical learning process, interest will play an important role, because PE requires interest to be able to enhance students' physical engagement during PE classes (Chen et al., 2019). Several other views agree that interest in learning is an impulse that arises in a person who can improve learning habits and learning outcomes. Consequently, Individual interest is associated with a person's propensity to participate in activities. Based on the results of the study, the high level of student attention in following PE learning was due to the magnitude of students' responses to attention to PE learning. The form of their desire to move in learning had come up because of a response or stimulus to the activities carried out. That was in line with the results of this research which revealed that the activities factor was defined as the majority in the high classification. Specifically designed activities according to differences in skill levels each student will provide support for the expected mastery of competencies (Otundo & Garn, 2019)

Theme 2. Explosive Punch in Fusion Teaching

In this theme the participants imparted that embracing creativity, the teacher navigates routine activities, employing motivational elements. Using different strategies in teaching like using video clips, lesson plan etc. serves as a structured guide, promoting a balanced sequence of instruction to the learners.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

The participants emphasized the use of creativity in teaching, employing motivational elements and strategic video clip integration. A detailed lesson plan serves as a structured guide, fostering exploration and incorporating Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) questions for interactive classrooms. The teaching strategy extends to performance tasks across subjects, inspiring comprehensive and enthusiastic learning.

Themes	Sample Responses	Participants
2. Explosive punch in Fusion Teaching	<p><i>“Madalas nagsisimula kami sa review ng previous lesson then pinapakita ko sa kanila yng mga ndownload ko na video sa youtube para magkaroon sila ng idea since hndi ko kayang ituro nang actual .Then duon na mgsisismula ang discussion nmin and kapag may time lalabas kami pra gawin nila but if wala nang time ayun next meeting nalang nila naipeperform”.</i></p> <p><i>“We start with a review of the previous lesson, and then I show them videos I downloaded from YouTube to give them an idea since I can't demonstrate it live. After that, we begin our discussion. If there's time, we go outside for them to perform the activity. However, if there's no time, they do the performance in the next meeting”.</i></p> <p><i>“Pinapapunta po sila dyan then binibigay ko lang po yng instructions then facilitite po sa mga bata. Kapag performance or mga task”.</i></p>	<p>Teacher A handling grade 7,8,9</p> <p>Teacher B handling grade 9 and 10</p>

	<p><i>“Yung routinary activity. May review may konting motivation and energizer. Hindi na ako nag unlocking of words kasi natouch nman yun sa ibang subject. Tapos after that meron akong mga video clips. Then after that yung mga certain activities naman yng mga outcome based activity namin may rubrics kami na kailangang ishare muna sa bata bago kami magexecute sa labas para alam nila ang gagawin nila at ibigay ang best nila pra kapag may indicators na ito ang pinakamalaki so kailangan nilang galingan”.</i></p> <p><i>“Our routine activity includes a review, a bit of motivation, and an energizer. I've stopped doing the unlocking of words since it has been covered in other subjects. After that, I incorporate video clips. Following the videos, we engage in specific outcome-based activities. We have rubrics that need to be shared with the children before we execute them outside so they know what to do and can give their best effort. This ensures that when there are indicators, they understand which aspects are crucial, prompting them to excel in those areas”.</i></p> <p><i>“Sa una palang nagpapakita ako if may materials na available ipinapakita ko na sa kanila. So duon palang kapag nakita na nila na hawak ko makikita mona yung reaction na gusto nila. Pero kapag minsan kapag wala ka naipakita na picture at hindi available wala ang interest ng bata. Hal yng bola hahawakan mo alam na alam na kagad nila na yun ang lesson</i></p>	<p>Teacher C handling grade 7,8,9,and 10.</p>
--	--	---

	<p><i>magtatanong na kagad sila na mam maglalaro naba tayo?”</i></p> <p><i>“At first, I will show them the materials that are available. Right there and then you can see their reaction that they are interested. But sometimes if you cannot provide material or even a picture you can see that they are not interested. For example, you will hold and show them a ball they already know the lesson and they will immediately ask “Mam are we going to play?”</i></p> <p><i>“Ano po through the guide of the lesson plan. Inexecute ko pa din kng ano yng pagkakasunod sunod ng lesson plan. Magbibigay muna ako ng konting lesson then actual na. There are times nman na pagpreresent ako ng mga video clips sa kanila imbis na sila ang nagpeperform. sinasabi ko na sa bahay nIng nila gawin kung meron”</i></p> <p><i>“Through the guidance of the lesson plan, I still execute the sequence outlined in it. I typically begin by providing a brief lesson, and then we proceed to the practical application. There are instances when I present video clips instead of having them perform.</i></p> <p><i>“Guided kami ng MELC. Sa DLL na ginagawa namin kagaya sa ibng subject duon kami nakasunod. Sa grade 10 ang PE nila ay recreational activity. Kasama po duon yung mga games like shuttleminton mga physical fitness test din meron sila. Health Related and skill related.</i></p> <p><i>“We are guided by MELC. We</i></p>	<p>Teacher D handling grade 7 and 8.</p> <p>Teacher E handling grade 8,9,and 10.</p>
--	---	--

	<p><i>follow the same approach as in other subjects, adhering to the Detailed Lesson Plan (DLP). In grade 10 PE there is a recreational activity. Like shuttleminton and even the physical fitness test. Health Related and Skill Related.</i></p> <p><i>“Sa umpisa po nagtatanong ako kng familiar ba sila dun sa lesson nmin. Tpos nafamiliarize na sila dun nako magsisismula unti unti tpos kpag alam na nila lhat duon na kami nag aactivity. Discussion muna bago kami nag activity”.</i></p> <p><i>“At first, I will ask them if they are familiar in our lesson. Then if they are familiarized with the lesson, I will start my discussion before giving them the activity.</i></p> <p><i>“More on exploratory minsan kasi iba iba ang approach ko e minsan naman naka video tpos tatanungin ko sila kng ano ang masasabi nila sa napanood nila”.</i></p> <p><i>“We often focus on an exploratory approach, and sometimes I vary my methods, such as incorporating videos. I then ask them for their thoughts and opinions on what they have watched”.</i></p>	<p>Teacher F handling grade 7 and 8</p> <p>Teacher G handling grade 8 and 9.</p>
--	--	--

The adaptability to substitute live demonstrations with videos, the emphasis on interactive learning, and the flexibility in scheduling outdoor activities contribute to a well-rounded and student-focused teaching approach. By fostering exploration and incorporating

Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) questions, the classroom becomes an interactive space where students thrive. Culminating in performance tasks across multiple subjects, the teaching strategy embodies a dynamic fusion that inspires comprehensive and enthusiastic learning. A notable strategy highlighted is the incorporation of Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) questions. This approach fosters exploration and turns the classroom into an interactive space where students thrive intellectually. By encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving, non-physical education teachers contribute to a holistic and comprehensive learning environment.

As an educator, these insights prompt reflection on the importance of creative teaching methods and structured planning. The acknowledgment of routine activities in physical education requires innovative approaches to maintain student engagement. The incorporation of motivational elements, video clips, and HOTS questions not only enhances the learning experience but also but also aligns with the energetic and dynamic nature of physical education.

Dynamic Teaching Fusion or an innovative and adaptive approach to teaching that combines various dynamic and effective teaching methods or elements to enhance the overall learning experience. The teaching of PE is a continuous process, which

intrinsically depends on new theories evolving that support effective pedagogy to the teaching-learning process (ParraGonzález et al., 2021; Steinberg et al., 2020; Zach, 2020). Recently, and following the avant-garde theories that emphasize the reorganization of the process of motor development and performance in a school context, contemporary teaching models have been promoting innovative processes in the form of student development (Gimazutdinov, 2020). These teaching approach involves a structured sequence of activities, starting with a review of the previous lesson.

2. What are the challenges faced by the non-PE major in teaching Physical Education in last mile school, particularly in utilizing educational technology?

Three themes were developed from the participants responses upon exploring the challenges of the non-PE major teaching Physical education in last mile school: (3) **Knock -out in space for Physical Education class** (4) **Game Over in the resources** (5) **Challenges of integrating technology is it IN or OUT**

Theme 3: Knock -out in space for Physical Education class

In this theme the participants revealed that the school's struggle with limited facilities, particularly the absence of a covered court and space for PE class. This has led to constraints in conducting outdoor activities, weather-related challenges, and creative fun games.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Theme	Sample Responses	Participant s
<p>3. Knock-out in space for Physical Education class</p>	<p><i>“Sa ngayon Physical Fitness testing mga curl up sit ups so ginagawa namin sya dyan sa may covered court pero maliit lang ang court namin. Tpos meron silang Social Dances yun nag gaganun din kami. Minsan nag dodown load sila pagdating nila dito nka download na. Dito na din sila nag practice. Ayoko nang nag practice sila sa labas kasi ang lalayo ng sitio nila”.</i></p> <p><i>“Currently, we are conducting Physical Fitness testing, particularly curl-up sit-ups, in the covered court. We perform the actual exercises there. We also engage in Social Dances, and sometimes they download the dances before coming here, I prefer not to have them practice outside because their residences are quite far”.</i></p> <p><i>“Sa covered court sila nag PE kpag discussion po nsa loob kami ng classroom. Kapag performance sa labas sila”.</i></p> <p><i>“They have their Physical Education class in the covered court, while our discussions take place inside the classroom. When it comes to performances, they do it outside”.</i></p> <p><i>“Maliit lang ang space namin so dito lang kami sa gilid. Wala kaming covered court dahil ang lupa na kinatatayuan ng schl ay pag aari ng mga Araneta at wala itong papel kaya hindi matayuan ng covered court”.</i></p> <p><i>“We only have limited space, so we stay here on the side. We don't</i></p>	<p>Teacher A grade 7,8,9.</p> <p>Teacher B handling 9 and 10</p> <p>Teacher C handling 7,8,9,10.</p>

	<p>have a covered court because the land on which the school stands is owned by the Aranetas, and it lacks proper documentation, preventing the construction of a covered court”.</p> <p>“Yung standard na room kasi naman hindi na kami nagkakasya kasi malalaki nay ng mmga bata sa grade 10. Yung culminating activity naming ay ditto sa covered court.Sa stage minsan like last week nagkaroon kami ng mini Zumba lng by group yun so sa court kami nagconduct pra lahat ay accommodated”.</p> <p>“The standard-sized rooms are no longer sufficient for us because the Grade 10 students are already quite tall. Our culminating activity took place here in the covered court. On the stage, we recently had a mini-Zumba activity, organized by group, and we conducted it on the court to accommodate everyone”.</p> <p>“Sa classroom kami mag klase pro kpag mga games lumalabas kami sa ground. Dito lang kami sa may ground wala kasi kaming covered court.Open lng sya sa ilalim ng punong Sampaloc.Kapag naambon sumisiong muna kami”.</p> <p>“We conduct classes in the classroom, but when it comes to games, we go outside to the ground. We only have this open area under the Sampaloc tree; unfortunately, we don't have a covered court. If it rains, we seek shelter underneath the tree”.</p> <p>“Minsan po kpag may mga nag PE sa labas duon lng kami sa harapan ng clasrrom sa may stage lng kami.</p>	<p>Teacher D handling grade 7 and 8.</p> <p>Teacher E handling grade 8,9,10.</p> <p>Teacher F handling and 8.</p>
--	---	---

	<p><i>Minsan naman sa loob lng kami ng room pinapatabi ko yng mga upuan sa gilid or minsan pinalalabas ko nlng pra magkasya kami”.</i></p> <p><i>“When there are Physical Education activities outside, we stay in front of the classroom, near the stage. Sometimes, we stay inside the room, and I arrange the chairs along the sides, or sometimes, I just let them go outside to have more space”.</i></p> <p><i>“More on outside dito sa ground kasi hndi na uubra sa loob ng room kasi marami sila. Wala kaming covered court. Naghahanap kami ng malilim na lugar”.</i></p> <p><i>“We focus more on outdoor activities here on the grounds because it won't work inside the room due to their large number. We don't have a covered court. We look for open spaces instead”.</i></p> <p><i>“Kapag may gumagamit po ng court sa classroom po kami pro most of the time sa covered court kami kapag physical activity”.</i></p> <p><i>“When someone is using the court, we use the classroom, but most of the time, we use the covered court for physical activities”.</i></p>	<p><i>Teacher G handling grade 8 and 9.</i></p> <p><i>Teacher H handling grade 7,8,9,10.</i></p>
--	---	--

It uncovered the Challenges in Physical Education Facilities and Space, emphasizing ongoing issues with limited resources, particularly the absence of a covered court and other venue which has posed difficulties in conducting outdoor activities. Weather-

related challenges and the necessity for creative adaptations within existing spaces further compound these constraints

The lack of optimal outdoor experiences may impact the variety and scope of activities, potentially affecting student engagement and learning outcomes.

It is fair to say that when you are teaching in a limited space, you cannot achieve the full amount of physical activity desired. Restriction of movement is very evident that may hinder the objectives of Physical Education which is learning by doing. The lack of optimal outdoor experiences may impact the variety and scope of activities, potentially affecting student engagement and learning outcomes. Overall, the theme highlights the significance of addressing these challenges to improve the overall physical education experiences for both teachers and students.

Challenges in Physical Education Facilities and Space as well as inadequate training for teachers on information and communication technology. Zhu and Wang's (2020) research highlighting issues with inadequate space to engage in physical activity is consistent with these findings. However, they were compelled to start the process of transitioning to the new and prescribed system of delivery, Furthermore, due to technological difficulties and a dearth of resources, teachers also reported difficulty maintaining student involvement during learning. Henrique et al. (2021) found that

learners in remote learning lacked social interaction and physical activity. Without classes, learners have difficulty remaining active.

Theme 4: Game Over in the resources

What surfaced in this theme is the importance of the resilience of teachers in overcoming resource constraints and their commitment to providing enriching learning experiences in PE through inventive approaches. This survey underscores the educational landscape's resource challenges, particularly in the realm of Physical Education (PE) instruction. The recurring themes of limited modules and textbooks, coupled with innovative responses from educators, highlight a dynamic shift towards technology, supplementary teaching methods, and a recognition of students' visual learning preferences.

It revealed the importance of dealing with the scarcity of resources and Fostering Innovation in Physical Education Instruction Theme 2 underscores the resilience of teachers in overcoming resource constraints in Physical Education (PE) instruction. Participants highlight challenges in educational resources, prompting innovative solutions such as technology integration, supplementary methods, and addressing students' visual learning preferences.

	<p><i>There is a television there, so they can watch videos. They also have modules and textbooks. In my opinion, additional resources are needed because, for me, the references currently available seem insufficient. Since it's not my major, I need to find materials to teach Physical Education to them</i></p> <p><i>“Meron naman po kaya lng kulang yng mga books. Mga text book lng ang available dito. Minsan nga 5 piraso lang kaya ang gagawin ko na lng ay isusulat sa Manila paper.kapg groupings nman magshare nlng sila ng books per group.Minsan may mga hndi ka Makita na topic sa text book nan as learning competency. Ngayon na lang naman nagkaroon ng module nang nag pandemic dati wala.</i></p> <p><i>"There are some resources, but the books are insufficient. Only textbooks are available here. Sometimes, there are only 5 copies, so what I do is write the content on Manila paper. For group activities, they can share the available books per group. Sometimes, the topics in the learning competency are not found in the textbook. Modules were only introduced during the pandemic, there were none before."</i></p> <p><i>“Meron kaming Learning materials aside sa video clips yung iba naman may actual materials kami like yng bola meron naman kami kaya lang kulang.</i></p> <p><i>“We have learning materials aside from video clips. We also have materials like ball but it is insufficient.</i></p> <p><i>“Meron kaming module pro limited</i></p>	<p>Teacher B handling grade 9 and 10.</p> <p>Teacher C handling grade 7 and 8.</p> <p>Teacher D</p>
--	---	---

	<p><i>lang ang bilang kaya one is to 2 kasi konti lng tlga. Yung supply hndi sapat sa bilang".</i></p> <p><i>"We have modules, but the quantity is limited, so it's typically one module for every two students.</i></p> <p><i>"Yung galing po sa deped na ginamit noong Pandemic na module yun pa din po ginagamit nmin. Kaya yng ibng activity hndi nmin maiapply since nka home based sya.Kami as teacher research, youtube ang mas ginagamit nmin. Mas magnda kasi na marami kang pinag kukuhaan maliban sa module lang".</i></p> <p><i>"Even during the pandemic, we continue to use the modules provided by DepEd. However, some activities from the module are challenging to implement because they are designed for home-based learning. As teachers, we heavily rely on research and YouTube to enhance our teaching methods. Having a variety of sources is beneficial, as it allows us to access diverse materials beyond just the modules."</i></p> <p><i>"Madalas po na ginagamit ko na teaching materials mga ICT talaga mga TV loptop. Ang module naman ginagamit namin pinapauwi namin sa kanila halimbawa mga Holiday ganyan pra may activity pa din silang nsasagutan khit nsa bahay sila pra hndi kami nahuhuli sa lesson. Yun po ang purpose sa amin ng module. Visual Learner na po kasi sila e. Ayaw na nila ng mga mahabang basahin".</i></p> <p><i>"Most of the time, I utilize ICT tools such as TVs and laptops as my primary teaching materials. We use modules, and sometimes we send them home for activities, especially</i></p>	<p>handling grade 7 and 8.</p> <p>Teacher E handling grade 8,9, and 10.</p> <p>Teacher G handling grade 8 and 9.</p>
--	---	--

during holidays, to ensure they continue with their learning even while at home. This way, we avoid falling behind in our lessons. The purpose of using modules for us is to accommodate visual learners, as students nowadays prefer visual content over lengthy readings."

Dealing with Scarcity of Resources suggests addressing difficulties related to limited resources while actively promoting creative and forward-thinking approaches in the teaching of physical education. In the PE context, first, teachers can support autonomy by showing interest in students' feelings and preferences, offering them a relevant space for decision-making, or fostering a climate in which they can freely express their sentiments Reeve & Cheon (2021). Second, teachers can support their students' competence in the classroom by providing structure both before the activity, such as by setting clear expectations or adapting tasks to the students' level of skill, and during the activity, such as by providing effective feedback and thus guiding the learning process. Lastly, relatedness support is characterized by the creation of warm contexts where teachers are empathetic, caring, and understanding of their students.

Theme 5: Dive into challenges of integrating technology is it IN or OUT

This theme delves into the resourceful integration of technology in education, particularly in Physical Education instruction. Teachers showcase a proactive role, bridging gaps in resources by utilizing TVs, laptops, and the internet, even in areas with sporadic connectivity. The theme emphasizes the transformative impact of visual aids, such as PowerPoint presentations and video clips, to enhance student engagement and understanding. It underscores educators' adaptability, resourcefulness, and commitment to leveraging technology for effective and innovative teaching practices.

Theme	Sample Responses	Participant s
5.Dive into Challenges of integrating technology	<p><i>“Yung technology na ginagamit nila dito na din nangagaling kami na din ang nagprovide. Sa ngayon mamalaking tulong ang pagamit ng internet. Pagkahalimbawa nsa seminar ako mag send ako na ireview nyo to panoorin nyo kasi pagdating ko gagawin ntin yan.</i></p> <p><i>"Here, we also provide the technology they use. Currently, the internet is a significant help. For instance, when I'm in a seminar, I send a message like 'Review this, watch it because we'll do it when I get back.' I show them exercises like curl-ups and sit-and-reach through videos. I tell them to watch it so that when I arrive, we won't spend too much time explaining, and they already have an idea of how to perform it”.</i></p>	<i>Teacher A handling grade 7,8,9.</i>

	<p><i>“Wala pa po kasi last week lang kami nagsimula sa PE. Kasi MAPEH po hawak ko kya 4 so iniisa isa ko pa po. Wala akong masyadong ngagamit sa technology maliban sa tv.May internet nman po ay sa youtube ako kumukuha ng mga ituturo ko.”</i></p> <p><i>"We haven't started yet because we just began with PE last week. Since I handle MAPEH, I'm taking it one step at a time for each subject. I don't use technology much, except for the TV. I do have internet, so I get what I teach from YouTube."</i></p>	<p>Teacher B handling grade 9 and 10.</p>
	<p><i>“Sa pagamit ng technology dahil walang internet ditto ay pumupunta pa ako ng bayan tpos nagdownload ako sa lop top na bigay nang deped na ginagamit ko sa ngayon pra may ipapakita o ipapanood ako sa knila. Minsan nagprint ako sa bond paper pra may maipakita sa kanila”.</i></p> <p><i>In using technology because there's no internet here, I go to the town and download on the laptop provided by DepEd, which I currently use to have something to show or play for them. Sometimes, I print on bond paper to have something to show them</i></p>	<p>Teacher C handling grade 7,8,9,10.</p>
	<p><i>“TV ginagamit ko yan.Itong speaker ginamit din nmin yan last time.Tpos before last year halimbawa ang ginamit ko sa physical fitness test yung nag improvised lang ako ng ibang gamit.Minsan pinapupunta ko sila sa library kasi learning resource nmin ang library for research. Mga video Clips.</i></p> <p><i>"I use the TV. We also used this speaker the last time. Then, before last year, for example, I improvised some equipment for the physical fitness test. Sometimes, I send them to the library because our learning resource for</i></p>	<p>Teacher D handling grade 7 and 8.</p>

	<p><i>research is in the library. Video clips.</i></p> <p><i>“Ang nagagamit ko lang po ay yung power point and presentation of video clips. May tv nman pro yng magamit tlaga ng nmga bagong app like kahoot syempre hndi nman ngagamit kasi dpat may mga cellphone ang mga bata e hndi karamihan dito walang mga cellphone”.</i></p> <p><i>"I only use PowerPoint and present video clips. We have a TV, but it's challenging to use new apps like Kahoot because the students need cellphones, and most of them here don't have one."</i></p> <p><i>“Ginagamit namin mga TV sa loob ng classroom. Kaya tlgang pinagipunan talaga ng mga teachers na mkabili kami ng laptop. Dati mahina yng internet nmin pro ngyn pinursige ng principal nmin na mapalakas yng internet connection nmin kya umaabot na sa classroom pro kpag nsa dulo ka nagloading kya antay antay nalang hahaha”.</i></p> <p><i>"We use the TV inside the classroom. So, the teachers really made an effort to save up and buy laptops. Our internet used to be slow, but now our principal pushed to strengthen our internet connection, so it reaches the classrooms. However, when you're at the far end, you still need to wait because it's a bit slow, hahaha."</i></p> <p><i>“Buti nga po ngayon may internet na kami ditto sa school kahit paano. Nagagamit nan min ang tv sa classroom kaso kng walang laptop ang teacher wala ding silbi ang internet”.</i></p> <p><i>"Fortunately, now we have internet here in the school, at least. We can use</i></p>	<p><i>Teacher handling grade 7,8,9,10. H</i></p> <p><i>Teacher handling grade 8,9 and 10. E</i></p> <p><i>Teacher handling grade 7 and 8. F</i></p>
--	--	---

transformative impact of visual aids like PowerPoint and video clips, the theme highlights educators' adaptability and commitment to innovative teaching practices through technology.

Now a days incorporating educational technology is a big challenge, especially in the last mile schools. Limited facilities may mean restricted access to technological resources, impeding the implementation of innovative teaching methods. The need for training becomes even more critical, as non-PE teachers may require support in utilizing educational technology effectively within the context of physical education.

In my own point of view, the integration of technology not only addresses resource constraints but also aligns with the contemporary learning preferences of students. It reflects a shift towards dynamic, interactive, and visually engaging teaching methods, contributing to a more effective and enjoyable learning experience.

Empowering Education Through Technological Integration and Resourcefulness conveys the idea of leveraging technology and resourcefulness to strengthen and enhance the educational experience. It emphasizes the proactive use of technology and creative problem-solving to empower and enrich the learning process. In an article by Almusawi (2021), the author explored Physical Education teachers' perspectives on their readiness for

wearable technology integration and developed a conceptual model for integrating wearable technology as digital innovation in Physical Education.

3. How do the non-PE major teaching Physical Education in last mile school address these challenges?

Four themes were developed from the participants responses which can be categorized as their coping mechanism to address their challenges: (6) **Grand slam to Resilience and passion in teaching Physical Education.**

(7) **Unleashing potential through adaptive Physical Education teaching.**

(8) **Teamwork between school and community.** (9) **Game Plan in addressing the challenges.**

Theme 6 Grand slam to Resilience and passion in teaching Physical Education

This theme unveils the resilience and dedication of educators facing challenges in teaching Physical Education (PE). Despite limited resources and challenging conditions, teachers creatively adapt, using available technology, such as laptops and TVs, to enhance the learning experience. The theme accentuates the commitment to empower students through engaging activities, emphasizing the significance of performance-based tasks and localized sports.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Theme	Sample Responses	Participants	
6. Grand slam to Resilience and Passion in teaching Physical Education	<p><i>“Nang walang internet yun ang mahirap kasi ako as teacher kapag bumaba ako sa bayanduon ako nag download tpos ilalagay ko siya sa usbo kaya ilalagay ko sya sa loptop tpos yun ang ipapanood ko sa kanila.tapos magtyaga sila sa maliit na loptop duon sila manonood. Mostly kpag ball games nag localization na lng kami kasi wala namn kaming table tennis hndi nman sila mkakapag table tennis so kng ano na lnga yng available na meron kami. Lets say Volleyball kahit hndi marunong cge tira bsta at lease mkahawak sila ng bola at maexperience lang nila performance task na”.</i></p> <p><i>“When there's no internet, it becomes challenging. As a teacher, I have to go down to town to download, then transfer the files to a USB. I'll use my laptop, and that's what I'll show to them. They have to endure watching on a small laptop”.</i></p> <p><i>“We played volleyball there, even in muddy areas with grass. Mostly, when it comes to ball games, we localize because we don't have table tennis, and they can't play it anyway. So, we make use of whatever is available. Let's say volleyball—even if they don't know much about it, as long as they can hit the ball and experience the performance task”.</i></p> <p><i>“Yun na nga po yung hndi ko alam. Hal.yng topic nmin ngyn is exercise, hndi ako familiar kasi ng college hindi nman nmin ginawa yun. Hndi q alam kung paano gawin kailangan ko pa pong tingnan sa internet para maituro ko po sa kanila. Sabi ko nga po sa 3</i></p>	Teacher A handling grade 7,8 and 9.	Teacher B handling grade 9 and 10

	<p><i>hawak dun ako sa MAPEH nahihirapan".</i></p> <p><i>"That's the part I don't know. For example, our current topic is exercise, and I'm not familiar with it from college since we didn't cover that. I don't know how to do it; I need to check on the internet to be able to teach it to them. As I mentioned, among the 3 subjects that I handle the most difficult part is teaching MAPEH".</i></p> <p><i>"Sa akin mam ang pinakachallenging ay yung sas pag aaral ng itutro mo sa topic ng pe.Kasi kailangan ko syang pagpuyatan kailangan ko syang intindihin kailangan ko muna syang ipractice hal mga sayaw at steps kasi ituturo mo sya kinabukasan. Kailangan kasi tama pag execute mo. Kasi nga hndi ko major ang PE. Sa isports medyo ok lng pero pagdating sa sayaw hndi ko talga forte ang sumayaw.</i></p> <p><i>"For me, ma'am, the most challenging part is the preparation for teaching PE topics. I need to dedicate time to understand and practice them, especially dances and steps, because I have to teach them the next day. It's crucial to execute them correctly since PE is not my major. In sports, it's somewhat okay, but when it comes to dancing, it's really not my strength. English, I also use Tagalog."</i></p> <p><i>"Pinakachallenging is sa profiling ng amimg grade 10 lhat ng bata dito nahihirapan sila sa English at math sa pagintindi. So ang ginagawa ko nalng dun ay tinatranslate ko. Mahirap tlga sila umintndi tlgang pinagpapawisan ako sa pag eexplain.Nasasayang lang yng oras ng wala silang naiintndihan kaya nag taglish ako minsan.</i></p> <p><i>"The most challenging part is profiling</i></p>	<p>Teacher C handling grade 7,8,9,10.</p> <p>Teacher E handling grade 8,9,and 10.</p>
--	---	---

	<p><i>our Grade 10 students; all the students here struggle with English and Math comprehension. So what I do there is translate for them. It's really tough for them to understand, and I end up sweating to explain. Time is wasted when they don't understand, so I sometimes use Taglish.</i></p> <p><i>“Yung resources na meron kami dito ay limited. Kapag mag actual kami sa sports pupunta pa kami sa Makapik-kapik pra makagamit kami ng covered court nila na may ring pra mkapag basketball”.</i></p> <p><i>"The resources we have here are limited. When we conduct actual sports activities, we have to travel to a nearby place that has a covered court with a basketball ring for us to use."</i></p> <p><i>“Madalas na late sa pagpasok kasi mahirap ang daan dito like yng nang nkaraan nabaon yng gulong nmn. Mnsan nman naflat ang gulong kasi hnagnag sa bubong ng jeep may nkasakay kya minsan hndi nko nkapag klase sa PE dhil na late na ako ng pasok.</i></p> <p><i>Sa pagtuturoi nman walang kuryente kasi dito dati hndi na kami nagkakakitaan kpag hapon na kya cut na ang klase.”</i></p> <p><i>"Often late in coming to school because the road here is challenging, like what happened last time when our wheel got stuck. Sometimes, the tire gets flat because it rubs against the roof of the jeep, and there are passengers, so sometimes, I miss PE class because I'm late.</i></p> <p><i>In teaching, there's no electricity here because we used to not have meetings in the afternoon, so classes are already cut.</i></p>	<p>Teacher D handling grade 7 and 8.</p> <p>Teacher G handling grade 8 and 9.</p>
--	---	---

	<p><i>the kids, in my opinion. Another challenge for me is the hot weather, and when it rains, it becomes muddy. We don't have courts here.</i></p> <p><i>“Ang mga challenges na kinakaharap ko sa PE lalo na sa 1st subject ay mdalas ang mga bata pagod na kagad kasi yng iba naglalakad papasok sa school. At yung iba nman nagtatrabaho nang paguuling at gumagawa ng mga sticks pra may pangkain sila. Kaya minsan hinahayaan ko nlng sila na magpahinga.”</i></p> <p><i>“The challenges that I am facing especially in my 1st subject are most of the students are already tired because they just walk to school. Some of them have work like making a charcoal and making a sticks for their living. That is why sometimes I let them rest.</i></p>	<p>Teacher I handling grade 7,8,9.</p>
--	---	--

The participants reveal resilience and dedication in teaching Physical Education (PE) despite challenges. Teachers creatively adapt, using available technology like laptops and TVs to enhance learning. Emphasizing the commitment to empower students through engaging activities, it underscores the transformative impact of passionate teaching, fostering resilience and dedication within educators and students in the realm of PE

The struggles of managing energy levels and student exhaustion, especially in the last periods, showcase the educators' adaptability and understanding. Ultimately, the theme highlights the transformative impact of passionate teaching, fostering resilience

and dedication within both educators and students in the realm of PE.

In my own point of view, this theme illuminates the remarkable resilience and unwavering dedication of non-PE major on navigating challenges in the realm of teaching Physical Education in the last mile school. The constraints of limited resources and challenging conditions are met with creative adaptations, showcasing the use of available technology like laptops and TVs to enrich the learning experience. The theme underscores a deep commitment to empowering students through engaging activities, emphasizing the importance of performance-based tasks and localized sports. The challenges of managing energy levels and addressing student exhaustion, particularly in the last periods, highlight the educators' adaptability and empathetic understanding. These struggles underscore the educators' capacity to adjust to diverse circumstances, ensuring a positive and supportive learning environment.

Fostering Resilience and Passion in Physical Education emphasizes the significance of grit in physical activity—characterized by the dedication to long-term goals through patience and passion. [Orvidas,Burnette 2019], including continued long-term efforts despite the accompanying difficulties such as failure, frustration, and so on, that arise when achieving an

objective. High grit means that individuals are passionate about participating in PE and do not give up on difficult tasks, overcoming them with persistence and sincerity. In other words, if one feels pleasure toward PE through a positive experiences, academic grit is indicated, which positively affects PE-related attitudes, resulting in positive effects on life throughout adolescence.

Theme 7 The Unleashing Potential Through Adaptive PE Teaching

In this theme the educators embracing imperfection, prioritizing student engagement and performance. The theme illuminates their resilient spirit, navigating challenges with improvised solutions in resource-limited environments. A continuous learning journey unfolds as teachers leverage YouTube for lesson preparation, constantly refining their techniques. Passion for sports becomes a driving force, transforming initial teaching hurdles into enjoyable experiences. Collaborating with experts, attending seminars, and engaging in sports clinics empower educators to enhance their methodologies. Localization emerges as a strategic approach, modifying activities to align with available resources and student interests.

Theme	Sample Responses	Participants
7.Unleashi	<i>“Hindi na ako mamimili na perfect</i>	Teacher A

<p>ng Potential through adaptive Physical Education teaching</p>	<p><i>na magawa nila ang importante sa akin as teacher mkita ko lang na nagperform ok na sa akin yun".</i></p> <p><i>"I don't expect them to be perfect. What's important to me as a teacher is to see them perform, and that's okay for me."</i></p> <p><i>"Hinaharap ko siya sa pamamgitan ng walang katapusang pag aaral sa mga lesson na ituturo ko at sa panonood ng mga youtube ako nag babase pra sa araw ng klase ko mayroon na akong kaalaman kahit konti lng sa lesson naming".</i></p> <p><i>"I face it through continuous study of the lessons I will teach, and I base it on watching YouTube videos. By the time of my class, I already have some knowledge, even if it's just a bit, about our lesson."</i></p> <p><i>"Dahil siguro na enjoy ko na din yng pag tuturo ng PE prang sinisikap ko din na mkahanap ako ng source na ibigay sa mga bata.Tapos naghahanap nalng din ako ng mga mtatanungan na mas marunong. Hal. Yng mga rules ng game ng una hndi ko alama pro nang nka attend ako ng seminar duon ko nalaman na yun pla ang rules ng badminton.tapos unti unti naenjoy ko na din siya. Tapos sa sports clinic yng tamang pagtraining sa mga bata.</i></p> <p><i>"Perhaps because I'm starting to enjoy teaching PE, I find myself making an effort to find sources to provide to the students. I also look for experts to ask questions. For example, I didn't know the rules of the game at first, but when I attended a seminar, I learned the rules of badminton. Gradually, I started to enjoy it. Then, in sports clinics, I</i></p>	<p>handling grade 7,8, and 9</p> <p>Teacher B handling grade 9 and 10</p> <p>Teacher C handling grade 7 and 8.</p>
---	--	--

	<p><i>learned the proper way to train the children."</i></p> <p><i>"Pinag aaralan ko po ng mabuti at mdalas pinapalitan nalag nmin na medyo kahawig dunsang sa sports ngayun na alam naaming ituro at alam namin na babagay din sa studyante. Katulag ng basketball wala kaming court kaya pinapalitan nmin ng ibang tteam sports nababagay din sa mga bata localization po ginagawa naming".</i></p> <p><i>"I study it well, and we often modify it to make it somewhat similar to the sports we know and believe will suit the students. For example, since we don't have a basketball court, we replace it with other team sports suitable for the children. We do localization."</i></p> <p><i>"Sa akin po ginagawa ko ng mga unang taon ko sa pagtuturo ko sa PE naghahanap talaga ako ng mga reading materials sa internet at sa youtube pra mapanood ko at magaya ko ginagawa ko sya sa haraop ng bata pra masabi nila na ang teacher nila ay magaling din at may alam pro ang toto ginaya ko lng yun sa youtube. At sympre every week inaaral ko ang next lesson pra pag harap ko sa bata nkahanda ako at may maituturo ako sa kaanila".</i></p> <p><i>"In my first years of teaching PE, I really search for reading materials on the internet and on YouTube. I watch and imitate the techniques in front of the children so they can say that their teacher is also skilled and knowledgeable. But the truth is, I just copied it from YouTube. And of course, every week, I study the next lesson so that when I face</i></p>	<p><i>Teacher D handling grade 7,8 and 9.</i></p> <p><i>Teacher F handling grade 8,9 and 10.</i></p>
--	---	--

	<p><i>the children, I am prepared and have something to teach them."</i></p> <p><i>"Madalas kapag wala kaming mga kagamitan na available pra maituro ko nag improvise ako like sa basketball ayun gumagamit kami ng balde dahil wala kaming ring kasi mahirap din nman lumabas ng school bka may mangyari sa kanila ako ang mananagot dun".</i></p> <p><i>"Often, when we don't have available equipment to teach, I improvise. For example, in basketball, we use a bucket because we don't have a hoop. It's also challenging to go outside the school premises as I am responsible for their safety.</i></p> <p><i>"Sa unang 2 taon lang nman po ako nhihirapan pro habang tumatagal unti nunti ko na din nagustuhang ituro ang PE dahil kahit papaano ay mahilig din nman ako sa sports at yung mga pagsubok ay kinakaya ko na dahil halos napag aaralan ko na din sya".</i></p> <p><i>"During the first two years, I found it challenging, but as time goes by, I am slowly starting to enjoy teaching PE. It's because, somehow, I also have an interest in sports, and I can now handle the challenges since I have learned a lot about it."</i></p> <p><i>"Gumagawa ako ng plano. Plan A at plan B kung mawalan man ng kuryente ginagawa ko manila paper muna or pumupunta kami sa library duon muna tayo magbabasa at discuss at sa PE class lumalabas kami at gumagawa ng physical activity na hindi nman ginagamitan ng kuryente.</i></p> <p><i>"I create a plan, both Plan A</i></p>	<p><i>Teacher H handling grade 7,8,9,10.</i></p> <p><i>Teacher E handling grade 8,9,and 10.</i></p> <p><i>Teacher G handling grade 8 and 9.</i></p>
--	--	---

<i>and Plan B. If ever we lose electricity, I resort to using manila paper first, or we go to the library where we can read and discuss. In PE class, we go outside and engage in physical activities that don't require electricity.</i>

This theme encapsulates a commitment to accessible and enjoyable PE, even amid constraints. Educators constantly evolve, seeking reading materials and preparing weekly lessons to elevate teaching efficacy and provide engaging educational experiences for their students.

The participants reveal resilience and dedication in teaching Physical Education (PE) despite challenges. Teachers creatively adapt, using available technology like laptops and TVs to enhance learning. Emphasizing the commitment to empower students through engaging activities, it underscores the transformative impact of passionate teaching, fostering resilience and dedication within educators and students in the realm of PE.

Reflecting on this theme reveals the profound impact of educators who embrace imperfection while prioritizing student engagement and performance in the field of Physical Education (PE). The theme showcases their resilient spirit, adeptly navigating challenges in resource-limited environments with improvised solutions. This underscores their commitment to providing

meaningful and enjoyable experiences for students, despite the constraints.

"Unleashing Potential with Adaptive PE Teaching" suggests a focus on realizing and maximizing potential through the implementation of adaptive physical education instruction. Adaptive teaching in PE is the process of adjusting the activities students participate in during physical education lessons, the teaching style or the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students Myers (2023).

Theme 8 Empowering Physical Education Through Community Collaboration

In the realm of Physical Education (PE), resource limitations become opportunities for creativity and collaboration within this barangay community. The municipality's sports department plays a crucial role, bridging the gap by providing essential equipment such as chessboards and volleyballs. While the barangay's support is limited, external stakeholders, including NGOs, emerge as vital contributors. Teacher innovation becomes the driving force as educators navigate challenges, improvising solutions, and incorporating continuous learning. Despite constraints, sports facilities, especially courts, are pivotal to PE, fostering student engagement and aligning with the essence of physical activities.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

The quest for resources involves strategic coordination, with educators seeking assistance from various sources. Donations, both in-kind and financial, from municipal and barangay entities, external stakeholders, and private institutions contribute to enhancing PE programs. The barangay's supportive role, particularly during competitions and events, showcases a community united in promoting physical fitness. In this collaborative ecosystem, the local government and stakeholders respond to solicitations, providing trophies, medals, and sports equipment during intramurals. The spirit of community collaboration thrives as each entity, despite limitations, strives to empower PE, ensuring students have the tools and facilities needed to engage actively in sports and physical activities.

Themes	Sample Responses	Participants
8.A Team work between school and commu nity	<p><i>“Sa barangay LGU wala pa pero sa Munisipyo nakahingi ako sa sports dept. Nakahingi kami ng chess board and bola ng volleyball. Wala kaming nkukuha sa Baranggay mas marammi kaming nkukuha sa mga external stake holders mga NGO’s. Puro teacher’s innovation kami. Ang mga sports equipment nmin minsan kpag may nagdonate in kind binibili din namin. Minsan sa MOOE”.</i></p> <p><i>"In the barangay LGU, there is none yet, but in the municipal government, I can request from the sports department. We obtained a chessboard and a volleyball from there. We don't get much from the barangay; we</i></p>	Teacher A handling grade 7,8, and 9.

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

	<p>acquire more from external stakeholders like NGOs. It's mostly teacher's innovation. Sometimes, for sports equipment, when someone donates in-kind, we also purchase some. Occasionally, we use MOOE (Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses)."</p> <p><i>"Siguro yng court po. Kasi nang nag aaral po ako ditto wala pa po yan. Lupa lang dati kpag umuulan maputik kya nag pe kami sa classroom. Nagagamit din po yang court kapg may mga sports fest kaya related din po sya sa pe".</i></p> <p><i>"It seems to refer to the court. Because when I was studying here, it didn't exist yet. The area used to be muddy when it rained, so we played in the classroom. The court is also used during sports fests, so it's related to Physical Education (PE)".</i></p> <p><i>"Meron naman kapag intramurals pinapahiram nila kami ng mg venue sa barangay pinagbibigyan kami nni Kapitan. May schedule kami pra mkapaglaro mga bata.Nakipag coordinate kami sa barangay. Sa munisipyoi nman request nman kami ng metals sport equipment. Financial assistance meron nman galling kay vice mayor mga donations kaya pinapasok nmin sa adopt as school sa mga binibigay ng mga external stake holders namin".</i></p> <p><i>"They have something for us during intramurals; they lend us venues in the barangay, and the Barangay Captain accommodates us. We have a schedule for the children to play. We coordinated with the barangay. In the municipality, we requested medals and sports equipment. There is financial assistance, coming from the vice mayor</i></p>	<p>Teacher handling grade 9 and 10. B 9</p> <p>Teacher handling grade 7 and 8. C 7</p>
--	--	--

<p><i>yung iba nagbibigay ng mga trophies at medal yng iba nman sports equipments and yung ibnag stake holders nmin like yng mga supplier nmin sa canteen yan bnibgyan kami ng cash kay pinambibili nmin ng ibng sports equipments”.</i></p> <p><i>“We receive assistance from the local government. During our intramurals, we send solicitation letters to the councilors and the barangay. Some provide trophies and medals, while others contribute sports equipment. Our other stakeholders, such as the suppliers in our canteen, also provide cash that we use to purchase additional sports equipment”.</i></p>	
---	--

In the realm of Physical Education (PE), resource limitations become opportunities for creativity and collaboration within this barangay community. The municipal sports department of Rodriguez plays a crucial role, bridging the gap by providing essential equipment such as chessboards and volleyballs. While the barangay's support is limited, external stakeholders, including NGOs, emerge as vital contributors. Teacher innovation becomes the driving force as educators navigate challenges, improvising solutions, and incorporating continuous learning. Despite constraints, sports facilities, especially courts, are pivotal to PE, fostering student engagement and aligning with the essence of physical activities.

The quest for resources involves strategic coordination, with educators seeking assistance from various sources. Donations, both

in-kind and financial, from municipal and barangay entities, external stakeholders, and private institutions contribute to enhancing PE programs. The barangay's supportive role, particularly during competitions and events, showcases a community united in promoting physical fitness. In this collaborative ecosystem, the local government and stakeholders respond to solicitations, providing trophies, medals, and sports equipment during intramurals. The spirit of community collaboration thrives as each entity, despite limitations, strives to empower PE, ensuring students have the tools and facilities needed to engage actively in sports and physical activities.

Reflecting on this narrative unveils a powerful story of resilience and collaboration within the realm of Physical Education (PE) in a barangay community. Even though Rodriguez Rizal is a small municipality they still manage to provide the needs of the school particularly when it comes to sports development. The creativity and collective efforts of the school and LGU's are very evident. The municipality's sports department emerges as a crucial player, filling the resource gap by providing essential equipment such as chessboards and volleyballs.

The barangays and external stakeholders, including NGOs, play a vital role in contributing to the enhancement of PE programs. Teacher innovation becomes a driving force as educators navigate

challenges, improvising solutions, and prioritizing continuous learning to overcome resource limitations.

Empowering Physical Education Through Community encapsulates the idea of enhancing the field of physical education by fostering collaborative partnerships with the broader community. This approach involves integrating external resources, support, and expertise from the community to enrich the overall physical education experience. Physical education programs are not isolated within the school but are seen as an integral part of the larger community. Collaboration with community organizations, local businesses, parents, and other stakeholders can bring a wealth of resources, knowledge, and support to the physical education curriculum. Community engagement exists on a continuum from no engagement or few connections between schools and their communities, to interagency collaboration, to full-service community schools and community development, which reflect the most integrated relationship between schools and their communities (Valli et al., as cited in Hands & Cleveland 2023).

Theme 9 Game Plan in addressing the challenges.

To elevate the quality of Physical Education (PE), there is an urgent need for educators with specialized training in PE. The

interviewee's insights underscore the challenges when instructors lack expertise or passion in the subject, emphasizing the importance of targeted training and seminars for both PE majors and non-majors.

Theme	Sample Responses	Participant s
<p>9.Game Plan in addressing the challenges</p>	<p><i>“Sa akin napakaganda sana kung Mapeh teacher talaga yun trained. Kasi ako hindi nman ako mapeh teacher pro nag volleyball din nman ako nag badminton personally since sporty din nman ako nang bahagya naishare ko but what if the teacher is not sporty? May ganun siguro ang isang hardship namin.is yng hindi nmin maituro ng maayos kasi hindi mo nga major diba halimbawa ang mapeh nman is not purely pe kpag music wala na kpag hindi ka marunongkapag arts kung hindi ka artistic paano na yung pe paano kng hindi ka sporty at yng katawan mo hindi mo maigalaw dhil may sakit kna din paano na? Paano mo sila pagexercisin e ikaw nga sa sarili mo hindi mkapagexercise so yun ang mahirap kaya mas masarap sana kung meron kaming MAPEH major talga na iyun talaga ang tinuturo nya.</i></p> <p><i>“It would be great if the Mapeh teacher is genuinely trained in the field. Personally, I'm not a Mapeh teacher, but I have played volleyball and badminton since I am somewhat sporty. I've shared this with my students, but what if the teacher is not sporty? It could pose a challenge for us because they might struggle</i></p>	<p>Teacher A handling grade 7,8, and 9.</p>

“Ako ang ginawa ko before nagcocontact ako ng mga PE major. Kung kailangang magkita nagkikita kami like sa Mascap may tgeacher dun na nagtuturo sa akin sa Music. Nagtatanong ako halimbawa sa pagbeat ng Calabarzon at Rizal Mabuhay tinuturuan naman nya ako talaga.

“Before, what I did was I contacted Physical Education majors. If we needed to meet, we made arrangements to do so. For instance, at Mascap, there's a teacher there who taught me about Music. I would ask questions, like how to beat Calabarzon and Rizal Mabuhay, and she would genuinely teach me. For teachers attending training and seminars, it can also be done through in-service education or inset.

“Siguro mam mga seminars and trainings. Kasi ako nanonood lang ako sa mga youtube hindi namn lahat ng information na nakukuha ntin sa internet ay tama. Minsan iba iba din ang sinasabi tapos kapg pinanood mo kung paano naexecute may pagkakaiba din kung paano nila ginagawa. Sympre kpag ipapaliwanag ko na nahahati din ako kng ano talaga ang ipapaliwanag ko. Mga sports equipments monitor or audio visual room. Ngayn kasi naghihiraman lang kami ng TV. Kaya nagaantayan or schedule kami sa pagamit ng TV. Hindi sila sapat”.

“Perhaps, ma'am, more seminars and training sessions would be beneficial. Personally, I often watch YouTube videos, but not all the information obtained from the internet is accurate. Sometimes,

Teacher D
handling
grade 7 and
8

	<p><i>different sources provide conflicting information, and when you see how something is executed, there can be variations in the approach. Of course, when I explain, I also get divided on what I should emphasize. For sports equipment, having a dedicated monitor or an audio-visual room would be great. Currently, we just borrow a TV, and this results in waiting or scheduling conflicts for TV usage. The existing resources are not sufficient”.</i></p> <p><i>“Sa amin bigyan sana kami ng proper training kasi mahirap magturo ng hndi namin inaral. Mga seminars. Kasi yung mga gamit kaya naming gawan ng paraan e. Pero yung pagtuturo ng skills na hndi nmin alam sana yun po ang magawan ng paraan na maituro sa amin”.</i></p> <p><i>We hope to receive proper training in our area because it's challenging to teach something we haven't studied. Seminars would be very helpful. We can figure out a way to address the lack of equipment ourselves, but teaching skills we are not familiar with is a challenge. We hope that can be addressed through training for us.</i></p> <p><i>“Ang talagang nirerequest namin ay expert teacher kasi kami nag aarla pa kami dagdag sa oras nmin yan. Kung sa major nga nmin nahihirapan kami kasi may mga topic jan na ayaw nmin skip dahil nga mahirap syang ituro how much more yung hindi namin major. So ganun kya ang kailangan nmin ay mga expert teacher as in major talga ganun. Also mga materials din na ginagamit sa pe class. Halimbawa k gaya sa</i></p>	<p><i>Teacher E handling grade 7,8 and 9.</i></p> <p><i>Teacher F handling grade 8 and 9</i></p>
--	---	--

	<p><i>Music wala din nmn akong alam alam sa music nayan kya ang gingawa nmin kumukuha lng kami ng mmga clips sa youtube. Ok nman kasi may pinag gagayahan sila. Sa art naman ayun localization na available ditto na materials na gagamitin Nila sa art. Pro most of the time wala kaming mga tangible maerials na ginagamit picture at video lang mdalas”.</i></p> <p><i>“What we really request is an expert teacher because we are still learning, and adding that to our schedule consumes our time. Even in our majors, we struggle, as there are topics we don't want to skip because they are challenging to teach, let alone in a subject not within our major. That's why we need expert teachers who are truly knowledgeable in that field”.</i></p> <p><i>“Una ang recommendation ko sana ay yng mag handle sana ng PE class ay yng PE major talaga pra mas tutok sila at maibigay nila yng learnings na dpat maaquire tlaga ng mga bata.Ako kasi sa sarili ko alam ko na not enough khita nagtry ako ng best kolalo na limited lng nman din yng skills na meron ako.lsa pa po ay sana maging complete ang facilities and equipments nmin ditto</i></p>	<p>Teacher G handing grade 7,8,9,and 10</p>
--	--	---

	<p><i>para kami mag actual hindi iisang bola lng ang ginagamit nmin. Pra hindi nag aantayan tpos mamaya lng time na tgpos na klase kya yng iba hindi na nkagawa. Anondin mam yng sa technology po. Although may ICT room kami pro iilan lng ang tablet. Also khit may internet kami hindi nman kayang maka connect ng sbay sbay ng mga bata. Mababa lng nag mbps nya. Para mka experience lhat hindi yung iba nkatingin lang”.</i></p> <p><i>“First, my recommendation is that those who handle PE classes should ideally be PE majors, so they can focus more and provide the necessary learnings that the students should truly acquire. Personally, I know that what I've done is not enough, even if I've tried my best, especially considering my limited skills.</i></p> <p><i>“Siguro mam mas aralin nang actual mas madali kasing ituro kapg inaral mo ng actual kaysa babasahin mo lang. Kagaya ng sinabi ko kanina sa Badminton kapag binasa mo siya ang hirap maintindihan pero kapag actual na ginawa mo sya mas maiintndihan mo para mas maituro mo sa bata ng tama. Yung sports clinic napaka importante nyan. Tska mahal nyo nlng yng subject na tinuturo nyo kasi sa ktagalan naenjoy ko na din ang pgtuturo ng PE at dhilsa lagi mo syang itinuturo at inaaral nagiging madai na din pra sa akin ang pagtuturo ng PE”.</i></p> <p><i>“Maybe, ma'am, it's better to focus more on actual practice. Teaching becomes easier when you've learned through hands-on experience compared to just reading about it.</i></p>	<p>Teacher I handling grade 8,9 and 10.</p> <p>Teacher H handling grade 7,8,9,10.</p>
--	---	---

Like I mentioned earlier, in Badminton, it's challenging to understand if you only read about it, but if you actually do it, you'll understand it better and be able to teach it correctly to the students. Sports clinics are crucial for this. Also, it's important to develop a genuine love for the subject you are teaching. Over time, I have come to enjoy teaching Physical Education because, through continuous teaching and learning, it has become more meaningful to me.

“Sana madagdagan pa yng mga equipment lalo na sa mga sports sana hndi lang isa sana yng sasapat sa bilang ng mga bata.

More on seminars and training kagaya nmin na hndi nman kami major ng PE at Mapeh hndi nman din spat na mabasa lng nmin sa libro mahalaga tlaga may proper training din kami. Mas mabgyan pa kami ng trainings sa hndi nmin alam. Sa mga learning materials nman kakaunti din mnsan kaya nag papa per group nlng kami na may isang module. Minsa nman sa mga batang nahuhuli yun pinapahiram nlng nmin ng module tpos pinababalik nlng nmin”.

“I hope there will be an increase in the number of sports equipment, especially for various sports, so that not just one set is sufficient for the number of students. Furthermore, additional seminars and training sessions would be beneficial, especially for those like us who are not majoring in PE and Mapeh. It's not enough to just read from a book; having proper training is crucial. It would be great if we could receive training in areas we are not familiar

	<p><i>with. Regarding learning materials, there's sometimes a shortage, so we resort to sharing one module per group. Occasionally, for students who fall behind, we lend them a module and ask them to return it later”</i></p>	
--	--	--

The theme emphasizes the necessity of additional learning materials, sports equipment, and diversified resources. This plea seeks to overcome the limitations faced by teachers, ensuring a more comprehensive and engaging PE curriculum.

Furthermore, the interviewee highlights the significance of proper facilities and technology, advocating for well-equipped classrooms, suitable audio-visual rooms, and a robust internet connection to enhance teaching methods and active student participation. In addressing organizational aspects, the call for dedicated spaces for PE activities aims to minimize disruptions and create an optimal learning environment for teachers and students alike. This theme encapsulates a holistic approach to advancing PE instruction through specialized training, enriched resources, and thoughtfully designated spaces.

The participants ‘urges specialized training for educators, emphasizing the need for targeted training and seminars in Physical Education (PE). It highlights the necessity of additional learning materials, sports equipment, and diverse resources to enhance the

PE curriculum. The theme also underscores the importance of proper facilities, technology, and dedicated spaces for optimal learning environments. Overall, it advocates for a holistic approach to advancing PE instruction through specialized training, enriched resources, and well-designed spaces.

Game Plan in addressing the Challenges.

A Call for Specialized Training, Resource Enhancement, and Dedicated Spaces the theme advocates for a holistic approach to physical education that goes beyond the classroom. It emphasizes the need for educators to be well-trained, for schools to invest in quality resources, and for there to be dedicated spaces designed to facilitate a comprehensive physical education experience. This multifaceted strategy aims to optimize the learning outcomes and overall impact of physical education on students' well-being and development. According to Kohl III and Cook (2023) concurred that the whole-of-school approach encompasses all people involved in the day-to-day functioning of the school, including students, faculty, staff, and parents. It creates an atmosphere in which physical activity is appreciated and encouraged by all these groups. School buildings, outdoor grounds and playgrounds, indoor and outdoor equipment, and streets and pathways leading to a school from the surrounding neighborhood encourage and enable all persons to be more physically active. Moreover, a school is part of a larger system

that encompasses community partnerships to help these goals be realized.

Essence

The lived experiences of non-physical education majors teaching students from last-mile schools delve into the unfamiliar and often challenging landscape these educators encounter. In these situations, teachers may lack a formal background in physical education, and they must navigate the unique needs and context of students in underserved areas.

This journey involves a process of understanding the specific challenges faced by students in last-mile schools, including potential limitations in resources, access to facilities, and diverse learning environments. Non-physical education majors must adapt and develop creative teaching approaches to cater to the unique circumstances and requirements of their students.

Resilience becomes a key aspect of these experiences, as educators face and overcome obstacles, striving to make a meaningful impact on the education and overall well-being of the students they serve. The essence of their experiences lies in the continuous learning, adaptability, and commitment to providing quality education in environments with limited resources and unique challenges.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions drawn and the recommendations of the study to further enrich the concepts and the facts conferred in the preceding chapters as provided by the results of the analysis of data.

Discussion

The following is the discussion of this study based on the Statement of the Purpose of this research.

As to the lived experience of non-PE majors teaching Physical Education from last-mile schools, has emphasized that students exhibiting high energy levels and genuine enthusiasm for outdoor activities during PE, preferring hands-on, active learning.

The participants also share their innovative and adaptive approach to teaching Physical Education that combines various dynamic and effective teaching methods or elements to enhance the overall learning experience even though they are non-PE major.

Based on the responses, all of them struggle in teaching physical activity because of the limited space and venue, resulting in constraints for outdoor activities and weather-related challenges.

Incorporating Educational Technology is another challenge to the teachers since the school is located where internet connection is

challenges with improvised solutions in resource-limited environments.

The shortage of instructional material like textbooks and modules leads to sharing of students that may hinder learning. They constantly evolve, seeking reading materials and preparing weekly lessons to elevate teaching efficacy and provide engaging educational experiences for their students.

The participants pointed out the importance of resilience in overcoming resource constraints and their commitment to providing enriching learning experiences in PE.

Majority of the teachers proved the fact that even though they are not PE major, the transformative impact of passionate teaching, fostering resilience and dedication in teaching Physical Education is the key to address challenges.

Practicing the innovative and adaptive approach to teaching that combines various dynamic and effective teaching methods or elements to enhance the overall learning experience.

The participants gave us a glimpse into the quest for resources involves strategic coordination, with educators seeking assistance from various sources. Donations, both in-kind and financial, from municipal and barangay entities, external stakeholders, and private institutions contribute to enhancing PE programs.

Finally gave prominence to the fact that advocates for a holistic approach to advancing PE instruction through specialized training, seminars, enriched resources, and well-designed spaces.

Conclusions:

In the light of the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

Teaching in last mile school is more fulfilling. The fact that some of the resources are not available or limited, teachers try to innovate and become resilient. Knowing that the learners enjoy PE subject the teacher responds to students' energy level, outdoor enthusiasm, and hands-on learning preferences with high spirit. Fostering a positive and dynamic classroom atmosphere that aligns with the positive and energetic nature of PE activities.

The importance of addressing infrastructure limitations, providing adequate training, and fostering a collaborative environment to enhance the overall physical education experience in last-mile schools. By tackling these challenges, educators can create a more conducive and impactful learning environment, promoting the well-being and development of students in these settings.

The dynamic relationship between technology and teaching, from facilitating communication and pre-lesson preparation to demonstrating exercises through videos, portrays technology as a

versatile ally. The narratives highlight the necessity of ongoing learning and the strategic use of technology as an essential component of professional development in the field of education

The strategies employed by non-physical education teachers to address challenges in teaching Physical Education showcase the power of creativity, detailed planning, and interdisciplinary approaches. These insights provide valuable considerations for educators seeking to enhance the overall learning experience, fostering enthusiasm and engagement among students in last-mile schools.

Passionate teaching fosters resilience and dedication within both educators and students in the realm of PE. Despite obstacles, the commitment to creative teaching methods and the recognition of localized sports as valuable components of the curriculum contribute to a dynamic and meaningful educational experience. This reflection accentuates the profound influence that passionate educators can have in overcoming challenges and fostering a positive and impactful learning environment in the field of Physical Education.

The challenges within the educational landscape, particularly in PE instruction, are met with resilience and commitment from educators who respond with inventive approaches. The importance of adaptability, technology integration, and a student-centric focus is

emphasized, contributing to a more robust and effective PE learning environment.

Educators embraced dedication, resilience, and continuous improvement in teaching the PE subject. Despite challenges, their commitment to accessible and enjoyable physical education is unwavering, demonstrating the transformative power of passionate teaching in the face of limitations.

The spirit of community collaboration thrives, portraying a shared commitment to empower PE despite limitations. This collaborative effort ensures that students have the necessary tools and facilities to actively engage in sports and physical activities. The narrative encapsulates the transformative power of collective action and resourcefulness in fostering a vibrant and engaging PE experience for students within the barangay community.

The holistic approach to advancing PE instruction emphasizes specialized training, enriched resources, and thoughtfully designated spaces. This multifaceted approach aims to create an environment conducive to effective and engaging physical education, contributing to an elevated experience for both educators and students.

Recommendation

The researcher offered the following recommendations for possible actions:

Teachers may tailor their physical education (PE) approach to the specific context of last-mile schools, prioritizing culturally relevant and engaging activities to enhance students' enthusiasm and engagement. Teachers may embrace resourcefulness to overcome constraints, fostering innovation in PE instruction and leveraging available resources effectively. Creating an Instructional Plan in teaching Physical Education that promotes localization suited for the last mile school is another possible action that will serve a great help and big relief to the teachers. Create an Instructional Plan in teaching Physical Education that promotes localization suited for the last mile school for school year-round.

In parallel, school administrators play a pivotal role by actively facilitating professional development opportunities for educators, emphasizing dynamic teaching strategies, resourcefulness, and the integration of technology into physical education. Administrators may invest in digital libraries with internet connectivity for E-books or downloadable reading materials in Physical Education.

Emphasizing the importance of infrastructure improvements is crucial to overcoming challenges related to facilities and space, thereby creating an environment conducive to effective PE

instruction. Creativity is the key in navigating challenges related to physical education facilities and limited space, requiring techniques and strategies that adapt to the unique environment of the last mile schools.

School administrators may actively facilitate professional development opportunities for educators, emphasizing dynamic teaching strategies, resourcefulness, and the integration of technology into physical education. Advocating the integration of technology in education guarantees schools access to digital tools that enhance the learning experience. The school may collaborate with other colleges and university offering bachelor's in physical education that are willing to adopt a last mile school and extend their program focusing on the pedagogy of teaching physical education to the non-PE major teachers.

Partnership with any Private sector that is upgrading their computers and willing to donate it for last mile school students.

Focal Group/team teaching, Mentoring and coaching of IT teachers to PE teachers.

Administrators may further promote collaboration among educators through initiatives that encourage resource-sharing and innovation. Acknowledging and supporting teachers in tailoring PE programs to align with the cultural context of last-mile communities is essential. Lastly, administrators may foster a school culture that

values resilience, passion, and inclusivity in physical education, ensuring a positive and sustainable learning experience for both educators and students.

Moreover, the local government could actively engage in collaborative endeavors to strengthen physical education programs in last-mile schools. Emphasizing investments in community sports facilities and infrastructure ensures accessible spaces for physical activities. Providing support for initiatives that introduce dynamic teaching methods promotes creativity and inclusivity in physical education. Fostering partnerships between schools and local businesses addresses resource challenges and spurs innovation in PE instruction. Encouraging community participation in shaping PE programs that resonate with cultural values is crucial. Heightening the awareness and appreciation for the pivotal role of physical education in building resilient, passionate, and healthy communities is essential.

As for the community, active collaboration is necessary to bolster physical education programs in last-mile schools. Advocating for investments in community sports facilities ensures accessible spaces for physical activities. Cultivating partnerships between schools and local businesses addresses resource challenges and spurs innovation in PE instruction.

Looking ahead, future qualitative researchers are encouraged to

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

conduct another inquiry about the phenomenon covering different locales of investigation and a different set of participants to explore further the studied phenomenon. Conversely, future qualitative researchers are also urged to conduct a similar study covering multiple locales and a relatively greater number of participants. This will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse aspects and contexts related to the impact of physical education in various settings.

References

- Almusawi, H. A., Durugbo, C. M., & Bugawa, A. M. (2021). Innovation in physical education: Teachers' perspectives on readiness for wearable technology integration. *Computers & Education*, 167, 104185. Chen et al., 2019).
- Datingaling, J. F. (2019). Specialization Mismatch in Teaching Senior High School Courses. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*.
- Del Pilar, E., & Millante, B. (2020). Teaching Non-Major Subjects: Lived Experiences of DepEd SHS Teachers. *Solid State Technology*.
- Department of Education. (n.d.). Retrieved from DepEd Memorandum No. 059, s. 2019.
- Department of Education. (n.d.). *School Infrastructure and Facilities*. Retrieved from <https://schoolbuildings.deped.gov.ph/lastmile>
- Gimazutdinov, R. G. (2020). Improving the Physical Health of Younger Preschool Children through Actuating Games and Walking Exercises. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 1340-1350
- GLOBAL, P. (2023, August 29). Retrieved from "Glaring" teacher shortage on school opening day needs "strategic" solutions - lawmaker:
<https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/08/29/2292294/glarin-g-teacher-shortage-school-opening-day-needs-strategic-solutions-lawmaker>
- Gomes, L., Martins, J., Ramos, M., & De Costa, F. (2023). The Impact of Non-Physical Education Teachers' Perceptions on the Promotion of Active and Healthy Lifestyles: A Cross-Sectional Qualitative Study. *MDPI-IJERPH*.
- Hands & Cleveland Håkansson Lindqvist, M., Mozelius, P., & Jaldemark, J.,. (2023). Higher education transformation towards lifelong learning in a digital era—a scoping literature review. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 1-15.2023).

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

- Henriques-Neto, D Marques, A., Henriques-Neto, D., Peralta, M., Martins, J., Gomes, F., Popovic, S., ... & Ihle, A. (2021). Field-based health-related physical fitness tests in children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, 9, 640028. (2021)
- Hernando-Malipot, M. (2021, May 10). *Manila Bulletin*. Retrieved from DepEd Prioritizes Last Mile Schools as Education Transitions to Technology: <https://mb.com.ph/2021/05/10/deped-prioritizes-last-mile-schools-as-education-transitions-to-technology/>
- Hernando-Malipot, M. (2023, August 24). *Manila Bulletin*. Retrieved from 20M students now enrolled for SY 2023-2024: DepEd: <https://mb.com.ph/2023/8/24/20-m-students-now-enrolled-for-sy-2023-2024-dep-ed>
- Hobbs, L., & Porsch, R. (2021). Teaching out-of-field: Challenges for Teacher Education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 601-610.
- Hwang, N., & Kisida, B. (2021). Spread Too Thin: The Effects of Teacher Specialization on Student Achievement. *Anneberg Brown University*, 1-31.
- Kohl III, Cook Hanauer, D. I., Zhang, T., Graham, M. J., Adams, S. D., Ahumada-Santos, Y. P., Alvey, R. M., ... & Sivanathan, V. (2023, November). Models of classroom assessment for course-based research experiences. In *Frontiers in Education*.
- Macasias, L. A. (2022). Knowledge and Skills of Non-MAPEH Major Teachers Teaching Physical Education. *IJAMS*, 39-59.
- Magsambol, B. (2022, June 24). *Rappler IQ*. Retrieved from List: 5 Education Issues that the Next DepEd Chief Needs to Address: <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/iq/list-education-issues-next-deped-chief-needs-to-address/>
- Myers, N. D., Lee, S., Chun, H., & Zhu, W. (2023). Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science (MPEES): A Summary of MPEES-Related Activities in 2022. *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*, 27(2), 85-96.

- Orvidas, K., Burnette, J. L., Schleider, J. L., Skelton, J. A., Moses, M., & Dunsmore, J. C. (2020). Healthy body, healthy mind: a mindset intervention for obese youth. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 181(6), 443-457
- Otundo, J. O., & Garn, A. C. (2019). Student interest and engagement in middle school physical education: Examining the role of supportive teaching. *International Journal of Educational Psychology: IJEP*, 8(2), 137-161.
- Parra-González, M. E., López-Belmonte, J., Segura-Robles, A., & Moreno-Guerrero, A. J. (2021). Gamification and flipped learning and their influence on aspects related to the teaching-learning process. *Heliyon*, 7(2).
- Pratiwi, N. W., Dewi, N. S., & Paramartha, A. Y. (2019). The reflection of HOTS in EFL teachers' summative assessment. *Journal of Education Research and Evaluation*, 3(3), 127-133.
- Raymundo, M. (2021). Teaching Non-Major Subjects: A Challenge to Senior High School Teachers. *The URSP Research Journal*, 34-41.
- Reeve, J., & Cheon, S. H. (2021). Autonomy-supportive teaching: Its malleability, benefits, and potential to improve educational practice. *Educational Psychologist*, 56(1), 54-77.
- Steinberg, C., Zühlke, M., Bindel, T., & Jenett, F. (2020). Aesthetic education revised: a contribution to mobile learning in physical education. *German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research*, 50(1), 92- 101
- Rental, H. (2023, September 18). *TES Magazine*. Retrieved from Why Non-specialist Teaching is Harming Retention: <https://www.tes.com/magazine/analysis/general/why-non-specialist-teaching-harming-teacher-retention>
- Sambit, M. (2021, July 5). *Linkedin*. Retrieved from Bridge Last Mile Connectivity for Equal Access to Education <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/bridge-last-mile-connectivity-equal-access-education-sambit-mohanty>

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Sorongon, V., & Castillo, C. (n.d.). *Making Distance Learning possible for Hard to reach, under-resourced and often makeshift schools*. Retrieved from <https://www.niras.com/projects/edtech-solutions-for-last-mile-schools-making-distance-learning-possible-for-hard-to-reach-under-resourced-and-often-makeshift-schools/>

Yumang, J. (2021). Bittersweet Moments in Teaching Non- Specialized Subjects among Senior High School Teachers. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 7-10.

Zach, S. (2020). Co-teaching—an approach for enhancing teaching-learning collaboration in physical education teacher education (Pete). *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 20(3), 1402-1407.

APPENDIX A

LETTER OF CONSENT

Dear Participants:

The undersigned is a Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management major in Physical Education at Emilio Aguinaldo College and currently working on her dissertation entitled, "**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJORS IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT LAST MILE SCHOOLS**"

I am interested in your experiences in teaching Physical Education at last mile school as a non-Physical Education major.

In connection with this, I would like to invite you to participate in this study. Your participation is voluntary, and rest assured that all efforts to protect your identity and keep the information confidential will be taken.

Please carefully read this consent form and signed if you wish to take part in this study. Should you need further clarifications, I may be contacted at my mobile number 09854763883.

Very truly yours,

MARIA HAYDE P. MARTINEZ

Researcher

Noted by:

LORNA A. ESPESO, PhD.

Adviser

Accepted by:

Participants's Name (optional) and Signature

APPENDIX B

PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

Teacher A	Teacher B	Teacher C	Teacher D	Teacher E
Grade Handled: Grade 7,8,9 Age: 40 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 8 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 9,10 Age: 29 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 2 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 7,8,9,10 Age: 35 years of age Gender: Male Years in Teaching P.E: 4 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 7,8 Age: 28 years of age Gender: Male Years in Teaching P.E: 1 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 8,9,10 Age: 45 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 10 yrs
Teacher F	Teacher G	Teacher H	Teacher I	Teacher J
Grade Handled: Grade 7,8, Age: 38 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 5 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 8,9 Age: 42 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 5 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 7,8,9,10 Age: 36 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 3 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 7,8,9 Age: 37 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 4 yrs	Grade Handled: Grade 8,9,10 Age: 39 years of age Gender: Female Years in Teaching P.E: 6 yrs

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

APPENDIX D

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

Non-PE major teaching PE at last mile school

Students during their classes and flag ceremony

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

APPENDIX F

PROOF OF CONSULTATION

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE
1113-1117 San Marcelino St., Parañaque, Manila 1757, Philippines | www.eac.edu.ph | (02) 8521-2719

Virtue ♦ Excellence ♦ Service

GRADUATE SCHOOL

2

ADVISER'S CONSULTATION SLIP

No.	Date	Purpose / Activity	Suggestions/ Comments of Adviser	Adviser's Signature
1	July 19, 2023	Confirm research direction and paper title	Try to focus on your professional work	<i>[Signature]</i>
2	July 25, 2023	Revising the Literature Review	Literature Review should be adjusted/divided	<i>[Signature]</i>
3	August 2, 2023	Revise the first three chapters of the paper	The content needs to be enriched and scientifically divided	<i>[Signature]</i>
4	August 10, 2023	Modify the format of the first three chapters of the paper	According to the EAC graduation thesis format	<i>[Signature]</i>
5	September 4, 2023	Defense of the first three chapters of the thesis	Completed according to EAC's initial defense requirements	<i>[Signature]</i>
6	September 20, 2023	Revised the first three chapters of the paper	Modified according to the comments given by the defense team	<i>[Signature]</i>
7	November 25, 2023	Writing an experimental plan	According to the research requirements and actual requirements	<i>[Signature]</i>
8	January 25, 2024	Selecting experimental subjects	Scientific division and grouping	<i>[Signature]</i>
9	February 26, 2024	Confirm the experimental plan	Adjust your timing plan and time	<i>[Signature]</i>
10	April 21, 2024	Conduct experiments as required	Follow the schedule to ensure the authenticity of the experiment	<i>[Signature]</i>
11	June 20, 2024	Collect and analyze experimental data	Use relevant software to record and analyze	<i>[Signature]</i>
12	August 20, 2024	Revise conclusions, summaries and recommendations	To correspond to the research questions and research significance	<i>[Signature]</i>

Manila Medco MEDICAL CENTER MANILA

Rev 05-11230522

